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An inexact Krylov subspace method for response
calculations in density functional theory

by Bonan Sun

Master Thesis

Examining Committee:

Prof. Michael F. Herbst
Thesis Advisor

Prof. Gaspard Kemlin
External Expert

EPFL Institute of Mathematics
MA (Bâtiment MA)
Station 8
CH-1015 Lausanne

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Abstract

Kohn-Sham density functional theory (DFT) is today the most popular electronic structure theory in quantum chemistry. In this framework, Density Functional Perturbation Theory (DFPT) is pivotal for computing various quantities that physically represent the response of the ground state density to external perturbations. The key building block of these response calculations is the computationally intensive task of solving the Dyson equation. It involves the iterative solution of a large linear system, wherein each iteration necessitates solving multiple smaller linear systems. In this thesis, we propose an inexact Krylov subspace method to dynamically adjust the tolerance of the inner iteration to accelerate the computation. We study the theoretical properties of the proposed method and show its effectiveness in numerical experiments. Our strategy can save up to 40% of the cost-dominating Hamiltonian applications without compromising the accuracy of the returned solution.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The electronic structure problem in quantum chemistry is a fundamental challenge, involving the solution of molecular Schrödinger equation. Despite the success of approximate methods, numerical computations of these structures remain a formidable task. Density Functional Theory (DFT) [28], a cornerstone of quantum chemistry and condensed matter physics, has undergone substantial evolution and represented a significant advancement in this area since its inception. This theoretical framework enables the calculation of ground state properties by electron density rather than wave functions, a more computationally feasible approach. The Kohn-Sham DFT [31], developed in 1965, becomes popular in the 1980s when practical exchange-correlation functionals obtained from quantum Monte Carlo calculations became available [15, 47] and is today the most widely used electronic structure theory in chemistry, materials science and other related fields.

Many quantities of interest corresponding to the response of a system to external perturbations can be computed by applying standard perturbation theory to the Kohn-Sham DFT framework, known as Density Functional Perturbation Theory (DFPT) [7, 21]. Its applications are vast and diverse. For instance, dielectric screening [48], phonon calculations [7], polarizability [24], analysis of SCF iterations [35, Chapter 3.4] and biological system simulations [17]. Despite its wide range of applications and success in various domains, DFPT is computationally demanding, particularly for large systems. The efficiency of DFPT is constrained by the critical task of computing the linear response $\delta\rho$ of the electron density ρ to a perturbation of the external potential δV , i.e., the solution of the *Dyson equation*. Many applications in practice require solving hundreds of Dyson equations to obtain the quantity of interest.

Mathematically speaking, after discretization, the Dyson equation is a large non-symmetric real linear system

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}, \quad (1.0.1)$$

where matrix \mathbf{A} is not explicitly available while the application of the linear operator \mathbf{A} to a vector \mathbf{c} can be computed by solving a series of smaller complex Hermitian linear systems

$$\mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{f}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (1.0.2)$$

In other words, the application of the linear operator $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_g}$ to a vector $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ is computed by

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{c} = \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N), \quad (1.0.3)$$

where \mathcal{L} is some multi-linear map and \mathbf{y}_k is the solution of the k -th small linear system in Eq. (1.0.2). In plane-wave DFT calculations, N_g is approximately 16 times of N_b . These equations are solved by iterative methods [51] since the matrices are not available explicitly. For the large linear system Eq. (1.0.1), we solve it by the *generalized minimal residual* (GMRES) method [52] with a tolerance $\tau > 0$. Each iteration i of the GMRES then requires to solve N small linear systems Eq. (1.0.2), which are solved by the *conjugate gradient* (CG) method [27] with tolerances $\tau_{k,i}^{\text{CG}}$. This procedure forms an *inner-outer iteration scheme*. Current implementations of DFPT typically fix $\tau_{k,i}^{\text{CG}}$ to be $\tau/10$ or $\tau/100$ for all the small linear systems Eq. (1.0.2) during all the GMRES iterations, which is suboptimal. In this thesis, we develop a strategy, based on the idea in [53], to choose $\tau_{k,i}^{\text{CG}}$ adaptively for different small linear systems Eq. (1.0.2), termed the *inexact GMRES method*. Numerical experiments demonstrate that our adaptive strategy can save up to 40% of the computational cost without sacrificing the accuracy of the outer GMRES iteration.

Structure of this thesis

The rest of the thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 2 introduces the mathematical formulation of the DFPT and does not assume any prior knowledge of DFT or even quantum mechanics. We start from the postulates of quantum mechanics and then derive DFT and DFPT. Chapter 2 concludes by discretizing the DFPT and writing down the linear systems Eqs. (1.0.1) and (1.0.2) explicitly. Chapter 3 introduces the Krylov subspace methods for solving linear systems and GMRES and CG methods as particular instances. Then we introduce the theory of the inexact GMRES method, which will be applied to DFPT defined in Chapter 2. Chapter 4 considers the application of the inexact GMRES method to DFPT theoretically first and then proposes two practical strategies to implement it. Chapter 5 contains numerical experiments to validate the effectiveness of the novel approach and compare it with the existing strategies. Chapter 6 concludes the thesis and discusses future work.

How to read this thesis

Readers of this text are assumed to have a basic knowledge of numerical linear algebra and functional analysis, which are covered by any standard textbook [57, 8]. While concepts from quantum mechanics and DFT are frequently utilized, no prior knowledge of these fields is assumed. A minimal subset of them that are necessary for understanding the thesis is introduced in Sections 2.1 and 2.2. Readers familiar with these topics may skip these sections. Similarly, basics of Krylov subspace methods are covered in Section 3.1, which can be omitted by those already knowledgeable in iterative methods for solving linear systems.

Chapter 2

Mathematical Formulation of Density Functional Perturbation Theory

In this chapter, we introduce the mathematical formulation of density functional perturbation theory (DFPT). We assume no prior knowledge of quantum mechanics and first introduce a minimal set of concepts in quantum mechanics. We then define the quantum many-body Schrödinger equation and introduce Kohn-Sham density functional theory (DFT) as a popular method to solve the many-body Schrödinger equation approximately. Furthermore, we introduce DFPT, which is a theory to compute the response of a molecular system to the perturbation of an external potential in the DFT framework. Finally, we discretize the DFPT and write down the linear algebra problem of interest explicitly in matrix form.

2.1 The quantum many-body Schrödinger equation

2.1.1 Postulates of quantum mechanics

In a physics theory, every physical object is mapped to a mathematical object according to some rules. The physical problem is first formulated as a mathematical problem by this mapping. The mathematical problem is then solved mathematically without any physical interpretation. Afterwards, the solution in mathematical terms is translated back to the physical world by the "inverse" mapping. Finally, the results are checked against the physical experiments and the mapping is adjusted until the results match the experiments. This is a general procedure of establishing a physical theory.

In classical mechanics, this mapping between physical and mathematical objects is so intuitive that we don't even notice it. For example, the position of a particle is mapped to a point in the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 and the velocity of the particle is mapped to a vector in \mathbb{R}^3 . The physical laws are then formulated as differential equations in \mathbb{R}^3 . The solution of the differential equations is then mapped back to the physical world. In contrast, quantum mechanics employs a more complex

and less intuitive mathematical framework. We introduce a minimal set of postulates of quantum mechanics that are necessary for the rest of the thesis in the section. We refer the readers to [6, Chapter 2] and [16, Chapter 3] for more details.

Quantum State: In quantum mechanics, a (*quantum*) *system* is the physical object or collection of objects that are being studied. Quantum mechanics postulates that all the information about a quantum system, i.e., the (*quantum*) *state*, is contained in a *state vector* ψ in a complex Hilbert space \mathcal{H} endowed with an inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$. The Hilbert space is usually an infinite dimensional function space

$$\mathcal{H} = L^2(\Omega, \mathbb{C}) := \left\{ \psi : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \mid \int_{\Omega} |\psi(\mathbf{r})|^2 d\mathbf{r} < \infty \right\} \text{ for some } \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n, \quad (2.1.1)$$

where the usual L^2 inner product is used. In this case, the term state vector can also be used interchangeably with the term *wave function*. A convention is that the wave function is normalized, i.e., $\langle \psi, \psi \rangle = 1$ and two vectors of length 1 that differ only by a phase factor $e^{i\theta}$ are considered to represent the same state.

Observables: The wave function does not correspond to any physical observable property of the system (e.g., position, energy, momentum, etc.). Instead, quantum mechanics postulates that physical observables are described by linear self-adjoint operators $A : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$, which are usually called *observables*. The eigenvalues of the observable A are always real since A is self-adjoint. The eigenvectors of A are called *eigenstates*. Quantum mechanics postulates that the only possible outcomes of a measurement of an observable A are the eigenvalues of A and the corresponding eigenstates are the states of the system after the measurement.

Hamiltonian and the Schrödinger equation: Among all the observables, the *Hamiltonian operator* H is one of the most important ones, which is the observable that describes the total energy of the system. In classical mechanics, the total energy for a particle of mass m with potential energy $V(\mathbf{r})$ in \mathbb{R}^3 is given by

$$E = \frac{|\mathbf{p}|^2}{2m} + V(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.1.2)$$

where \mathbf{p} is the momentum of the particle and $|\cdot|$ is the Euclidean norm in \mathbb{R}^3 . In quantum mechanics, the *momentum operator* p is defined to be a differential operator

$$p = -i\hbar\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}, \quad \psi(\mathbf{r}) \mapsto -i\hbar\nabla_{\mathbf{r}}\psi(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.1.3)$$

where \hbar is the *reduced Planck constant*. The *potential operator* V associated with the potential energy $V(\mathbf{r})$ is defined to be a multiplication operator

$$V : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}, \quad \psi(\mathbf{r}) \mapsto V(\mathbf{r})\psi(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.1.4)$$

With some abuse of notation, we usually use the operator V and the function $V(\mathbf{r})$ associated with it interchangeably. In the spirit of Eq. (2.1.2), the Hamiltonian operator for a particle of mass m with potential energy function $V(\mathbf{r})$ in \mathbb{R}^3 is defined to be

$$H = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.1.5)$$

By the postulates of quantum mechanics discussed in the previous paragraph, the energy of the system is an eigenvalue of the Hamiltonian operator. The eigenvalue problem

$$H\psi(\mathbf{r}) = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V(\mathbf{r})\right)\psi(\mathbf{r}) = \epsilon\psi(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2.1.6)$$

is known as the *time-independent Schrödinger equation*.

Remark 1. Although not of interest in this thesis, it is worth mentioning that the "Newton's second law" in quantum mechanics is the *time-dependent Schrödinger equation*

$$i\hbar\frac{\partial\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V(\mathbf{r})\right)\psi(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (2.1.7)$$

which describes the time evolution of the quantum state.

From now on, we will refer to the time-independent Schrödinger equation as the *Schrödinger equation* for simplicity.

2.1.2 Many-body Schrödinger equation

The Schrödinger equation for a single particle Eq. (2.1.6) can be extended to the case of N particles. Consider a system of N particles with masses m_1, m_2, \dots, m_N and potential energy function $V(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)$ in \mathbb{R}^{3N} . The wave function of this quantum system is then a function of $3N$ variables $\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) \in \mathcal{H}$ where $\mathcal{H} = (L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}))^{\otimes N}$ is the tensor product of N copies of the Hilbert space $L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C})$. The Hamiltonian operator for this system is defined to be

$$H = \sum_{n=1}^N T_n + V = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n}\Delta_{\mathbf{r}_n}\right) + V(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N), \quad (2.1.8)$$

where T_n is the kinetic energy operator for the n -th particle. The Schrödinger equation for this system then reads

$$\left(\sum_{n=1}^N T_n + V\right)\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) = \epsilon\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N), \quad (2.1.9)$$

which is known as the *many-body Schrödinger equation*. The particles are called *non-interacting* if the potential energy function $V(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)$ can be written as a sum of N functions $V_n(\mathbf{r}_n)$, i.e.,

$$V(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) = \sum_{n=1}^N V_n(\mathbf{r}_n). \quad (2.1.10)$$

In this case, the many body Schrödinger equation Eq. (2.1.9) can be solved by solving N single-particle Schrödinger equations

$$(T_n + V_n) \phi_n(\mathbf{r}_n) = \epsilon_n \phi_n(\mathbf{r}_n), \text{ for } n = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (2.1.11)$$

In fact, it is easy to verify that the eigenpair

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) = \prod_{n=1}^N \phi_n(\mathbf{r}_n), \quad \epsilon = \sum_{n=1}^N \epsilon_n \quad (2.1.12)$$

solves the many-body Schrödinger equation Eq. (2.1.9). We remark here there are some additional conditions on the wave function ψ to ensure that it is a valid quantum state. They are not relevant to the rest of the thesis and thus we omit the details here.

In a chemical system (usually a molecule or a solid), the particles are electrons and nuclei. Consider a system of N electrons and M nuclei. The wave function of this quantum system is then a function of $3N + 3M$ variables $\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \dots, \mathbf{R}_M)$. However, since the nuclei are much heavier than the electrons, the nuclei are usually treated as fixed point charges and the wave function of the system is approximated as a function of $3N$ variables $\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)$. This is the *Born-Oppenheimer approximation* [49] and the positions of the nuclei are fixed constants $\{\mathbf{R}_m\}_{m=1}^M$, which is called the *nuclear configuration*. The quantum state of these electrons is called the *electronic structure* of the system.

Let m_e , e and k_e denote the mass of an electron, the elementary charge and the Coulomb constant respectively. Let Z_m denote the atomic number of the m -th nucleus, which implies that the charge of the m -th nucleus is $Z_m e$. The potential energy function V for this system is the sum of all Coulomb interactions between the electrons and the nuclei and between the electrons themselves, denoted by V_{en} (electron-nuclei interaction) and V_{ee} (electron-electron interaction) respectively. Therefore, the potential energy function V can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} V &= V_{\text{en}} + V_{\text{ee}} = \sum_{n=1}^N V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}_n) + V_{\text{ee}}(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M k_e \frac{Z_m e^2}{|\mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{R}_m|} + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=n+1}^N k_e \frac{e^2}{|\mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{r}_m|}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.13)$$

where $V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}_n)$ is the electron-nuclei interaction felt by the n -th electron due to all the M nuclei, which is usually called the *external potential*. All the electron-nuclei interactions are summed up to get the total electron-nuclei interaction V_{en} . Then the Hamiltonian operator for this system is given

by

$$H = T + V = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \Delta_{\mathbf{r}_n} \right) + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M k_e \frac{Z_m e^2}{|\mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{R}_m|} + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=n+1}^N k_e \frac{e^2}{|\mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{r}_m|}. \quad (2.1.14)$$

We use the atomic units (a.u.) in this thesis, which defines that $\hbar = m_e = e = k_e = 1$. Therefore, the Hamiltonian operator for this system is given by

$$H = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \Delta_{\mathbf{r}_n} + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{Z_m}{|\mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{R}_m|} + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=n+1}^N \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{r}_m|}. \quad (2.1.15)$$

Quantum mechanics postulates that for a system of electrons, the $3N$ -dimensional wave function $\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)$ is *antisymmetric* with respect to the exchange of any two electrons, i.e.,

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_n, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n'}, \dots, \mathbf{r}_n, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) = -\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n'}, \dots, \mathbf{r}_n, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N), \text{ for } n \neq n'. \quad (2.1.16)$$

which is known as the *Pauli exclusion principle* [37]. The Hilbert space of all the antisymmetric wave functions is denoted by

$$\mathcal{A}_N := \left\{ \psi \in \bigotimes_{n=1}^N L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}) \mid \psi \text{ is antisymmetric} \right\}. \quad (2.1.17)$$

The many-body Schrödinger equation for this system then reads

$$H\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) = \epsilon\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N), \quad \psi \in \mathcal{A}_N \quad (2.1.18)$$

where H is the Hamiltonian operator defined in Eq. (2.1.15). The *ground state energy* ϵ_1 is the lowest eigenvalue of the Hamiltonian operator H and the *ground state* is the corresponding eigenfunction. The ground state energy is the key quantity in the electronic structure theory and can be viewed as an optimization problem by the Courant-Fischer min-max theorem [55, Chapter 4], i.e.,

$$\epsilon_1 = \min_{\psi \in \mathcal{A}_N, \langle \psi, \psi \rangle = 1} E[\psi], \quad (2.1.19)$$

where the *energy functional* E is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} E[\psi] &= \langle \psi, H\psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{3N}} \psi^*(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) H\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) d\mathbf{r}_1 \cdots d\mathbf{r}_N \\ &= \underbrace{\langle \psi, T\psi \rangle}_{=: E_T[\psi]} + \underbrace{\langle \psi, V_{\text{en}}\psi \rangle}_{=: E_{\text{ext}}[\psi]} + \underbrace{\langle \psi, V_{\text{ee}}\psi \rangle}_{=: E_{\text{ee}}[\psi]}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.20)$$

We note that $E_{\text{ext}}[\psi]$ is the only term that depends on the nuclear configuration, which also justifies the subscript "external". The other two terms are the same for any system of N electrons and therefore $E_T[\psi] + E_{\text{ee}}[\psi]$ is usually referred to be *universal*.

2.2 Kohn-Sham density functional theory (KS-DFT)

Tackling the many-body Schrödinger equation directly is computationally intractable. The main difficulty is the exponential scaling of the computational cost with respect to the number of electrons. This is known as the *curse of dimensionality*. For example, the number of grid points needed to discretize the wave function of a single electron in a 3D box with a grid spacing of h is $O(h^{-3})$. For a simple system of one aluminum atom with 13 electrons, even with a relatively coarse grid with each dimension having only 100 grid points, the number of grid points needed to discretize the wave function is 100^{39} , which is larger than the number of atoms in the universe. Therefore, different approximation methods are developed to solve the many-body Schrödinger equation, among which Kohn-Sham density functional theory (KS-DFT) [31] is one of the most popular and successful methods. We mostly follow the exposition in [30] and [35] in this section.

2.2.1 Kohn-Sham equations

DFT, as suggested by its name, reformulates the energy functional $E[\psi]$ Eq. (2.1.20) as a functional of the *electron density* $\rho(\mathbf{r})$, which is defined as

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) := N \int_{\mathbb{R}^{3(N-1)}} |\psi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)|^2 d\mathbf{r}_2 \cdots d\mathbf{r}_N. \quad (2.2.1)$$

The name "density" comes from the fact that $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ can be interpreted as the probability density of finding an electron at the position \mathbf{r} , i.e., the number of electrons found in the domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is given by $\int_{\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}$. In particular, the total number of electrons is given by $\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} = N$. The problem of finding the ground state energy is then reformulated as an optimization problem with the electron density as the variable instead of the wave function, which reduces the dimension of the problem from $3N$ to 3.

Formally, let \mathcal{D}_N denote the set of all the possible electron densities for a system of N electrons. Then the Hohenberg-Kohn theorem [30, Chapter 4] states that the mapping $\mathcal{A}_N \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_N, \psi \mapsto \rho$ is bijective.¹ With some abuse of notation, we denote this map and its inverse by $\rho[\psi]$ and $\psi[\rho]$ respectively. Therefore, the ground state energy can be written as a functional of the electron density, i.e.,

$$\epsilon_1 = \min_{\rho \in \mathcal{D}_N} F[\rho], \quad (2.2.2)$$

where the *density functional* F is defined by

$$F[\rho] := E[\psi[\rho]] = F_T[\rho] + F_{\text{ext}}[\rho] + F_{\text{ee}}[\rho], \quad (2.2.3)$$

where $F_T[\rho]$, $F_{\text{ext}}[\rho]$ and $F_{\text{ee}}[\rho]$ are just the $E_T[\psi]$, $E_{\text{ext}}[\psi]$ and $E_{\text{ee}}[\psi]$ in Eq. (2.1.20) with ψ replaced by $\psi[\rho]$. We note that the external potential energy $E_{\text{ext}}[\psi]$ is the only term that can be written

¹Note that this statement is not true rigorously. Here we just assume this for the clearness of the presentation. See [34] for details.

explicitly as a functional of the electron density ρ :

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\text{ext}}[\psi] &= \langle \psi, V_{\text{en}} \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{3N}} |\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)|^2 V_{\text{en}}(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) d\mathbf{r}_1 \cdots d\mathbf{r}_N \\
&= N \int_{\mathbb{R}^{3N}} |\psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)|^2 V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}_1) d\mathbf{r}_1 \cdots d\mathbf{r}_N \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{r}) V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} = F_{\text{ext}}[\rho].
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2.4}$$

where for the second line we have used the antisymmetry of the wave function in Eq. (2.1.17) to exchange the variables $\mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N$ with \mathbf{r}_1 . The other two terms $F_{\text{T}}[\rho]$ and $F_{\text{ee}}[\rho]$, which are universal as discussed in the previous section, are unknown and are usually approximated. $F_{\text{ee}}[\rho]$ is usually approximated by the *Hartree term*:

$$F_{\text{ee}}[\rho] \approx F_{\text{ee}}^{\text{H}}[\rho] := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r})\rho(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}'. \tag{2.2.5}$$

For the kinetic energy term $F_{\text{T}}[\rho]$, as we have seen in Section 2.1.2, if the electrons are non-interacting, then the many-body Schrödinger equation can be solved by solving N single-particle Schrödinger equations. The *Kohn-Sham density functional theory* (KS-DFT) is then motivated by this observation and postulates that there exists an auxiliary non-interacting system with the same electron density ρ as the interacting system

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2}\Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}) \right) \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) = \epsilon_n \phi_n(\mathbf{r}), \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \tag{2.2.6}$$

where $V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})$ is called the *effective potential* (to be determined). The electron density in this case is given by

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1}^N |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2, \tag{2.2.7}$$

where $|\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2$ can be interpreted as the probability density of finding the n -th electron at the position \mathbf{r} . Then the kinetic energy term $F_{\text{T}}[\rho]$ is approximated by the sum of all the single-particle kinetic energy terms:

$$F_{\text{T}}[\rho] \approx F_{\text{T}}^{\text{s}}[\rho] := \sum_{n=1}^N \left\langle \phi_n, -\frac{1}{2}\Delta_{\mathbf{r}} \phi_n \right\rangle = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} |\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 d\mathbf{r}. \tag{2.2.8}$$

Therefore, the density functional Eq. (2.2.3) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
F[\rho] &= F_{\text{T}}[\rho] + F_{\text{ext}}[\rho] + F_{\text{ee}}[\rho] \\
&= F_{\text{T}}^{\text{s}}[\rho] + F_{\text{ext}}[\rho] + F_{\text{ee}}^{\text{H}}[\rho] + \underbrace{F_{\text{ee}}[\rho] - F_{\text{ee}}^{\text{H}}[\rho] + F_{\text{T}}[\rho] - F_{\text{T}}^{\text{s}}[\rho]}_{=: F_{\text{xc}}[\rho]} \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} |\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 d\mathbf{r} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{r}) V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r})\rho(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' + F_{\text{xc}}[\rho],
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2.9}$$

where the remaining term $F_{\text{xc}}[\rho]$ after the approximations is called the *exchange-correlation energy*. We remark that up to this point, the Kohn-Sham density functional theory is *exact* if we have the exact exchange-correlation energy available. However, this is not known and is usually approximated by some physically motivated or data-driven formula. See [46] for a review of the exchange-correlation energy functionals.

Now, we will determine the effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})$ in the auxiliary non-interacting system Eq. (2.2.6). The wave functions of Eq. (2.2.6) are called the (*Kohn-Sham*) *orbitals* or *bands* and they minimize the Kohn-Sham energy functional since they should be stationary points of the energy functional. Writing down the Euler-Lagrange equations for the Kohn-Sham energy functional Eq. (2.2.9), with respect to the orbitals, subject to the constraint that the orbitals are normalized, we get the *Kohn-Sham equations*

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(-\frac{1}{2} \Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{H}}[\rho](\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{xc}}[\rho](\mathbf{r}) \right) \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) &= \epsilon_n \phi_n(\mathbf{r}), \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \\
\rho(\mathbf{r}) &= \sum_{n=1}^N |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2, \quad \epsilon_1 \leq \epsilon_2 \leq \dots \leq \epsilon_N, \quad \langle \phi_n, \phi_m \rangle = \delta_{nm},
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2.10}$$

where

$$V_{\text{H}}[\rho] := \frac{\delta F_{\text{ee}}^{\text{H}}[\rho]}{\delta \rho} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r}', \quad V_{\text{xc}}[\rho] := \frac{\delta F_{\text{xc}}[\rho]}{\delta \rho} \tag{2.2.11}$$

are called the *Hartree potential* and the *exchange-correlation potential* respectively and δ_{nm} is the Kronecker delta. The sum of them $V_{\text{Hxc}} := V_{\text{H}} + V_{\text{xc}}$ is called the *Hartree-exchange-correlation potential*. Here, $\delta F / \delta \rho$ denotes the functional derivative or variational derivative. We refer the readers to, e.g., [43, Appendix A] for details and [18] for a mathematical introduction. The operator

$$H[\rho] := -\frac{1}{2} \Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho](\mathbf{r}) \tag{2.2.12}$$

is called the *Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian*, which depends on the electron density ρ . Hence the Kohn-Sham equations can be viewed as a *nonlinear eigenvalue problem*. The effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})$ in the auxiliary non-interacting system Eq. (2.2.6) is then given by

$$V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}) = V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho](\mathbf{r}). \tag{2.2.13}$$

2.2.2 Density operator formulation

Consider a unitary transformation $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ and define the unitarily transformed orbitals $\tilde{\phi}_n(\mathbf{r}) := \sum_{m=1}^N U_{mn} \phi_m(\mathbf{r})$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Then it is easy to verify that the electron density is invariant under this transformation. As a result, $\{\tilde{\phi}_n(\mathbf{r})\}_{n=1}^N$ also satisfies the Kohn-Sham equations Eq. (2.2.10) and the Kohn-Sham energy functional Eq. (2.2.9) is invariant under this transformation. Therefore, it is natural to consider the subspace spanned by the orbitals $\text{span}\{\phi_n(\mathbf{r})\}_{n=1}^N$ instead of the individual orbitals. The orthogonal projection operator onto this subspace is given by

$$P := \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) \otimes \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) : L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}) \rightarrow L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}), \quad \psi(\mathbf{r}) \mapsto \sum_{n=1}^N \langle \phi_n, \psi \rangle \phi_n(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.2.14)$$

which is called the *density operator* and \otimes is the outer product. The term "density operator" is usually used interchangeably with the term "*density matrix*". It is easy to see that the density operator is self-adjoint and idempotent. Furthermore, it can be viewed as an integral operator

$$(P\psi)(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \langle \phi_n, \psi \rangle \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \underbrace{\left(\sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) \phi_n^*(\mathbf{r}') \right)}_{=: K_P(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')} \psi(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}', \quad (2.2.15)$$

where $K_P(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is called the *kernel* of the density operator. In particular, the *diagonal* part of the kernel is exactly the electron density:

$$(\text{diag } K_P)(\mathbf{r}) := K_P(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) \phi_n^*(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1}^N |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 = \rho(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2.2.16)$$

and the trace of the operator is the number of electrons:

$$\text{tr}(P) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} K_P(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} = N. \quad (2.2.17)$$

Then we can write the Kohn-Sham energy functional Eq. (2.2.9) as a functional of the density operator:

$$\begin{aligned} G[P] &:= F[\rho] = F[\text{diag } K_P] \\ &= \underbrace{F_{\text{T}}^{\text{s}}[\text{diag } K_P]}_{=: G_{\text{T}}^{\text{s}}[P]} + \underbrace{F_{\text{ext}}[\text{diag } K_P]}_{=: G_{\text{ext}}[P]} + \underbrace{F_{\text{ee}}^{\text{H}}[\text{diag } K_P]}_{=: G_{\text{ee}}^{\text{H}}[P]} + \underbrace{F_{\text{xc}}[\text{diag } K_P]}_{=: G_{\text{xc}}[P]}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.18)$$

where F is defined in Eq. (2.2.9) and the optimization constraint for minimizing the energy $G[P]$ is

$$P \in \mathcal{M}_0 := \{P : L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}) \rightarrow L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}) \mid P^2 = P = P^*, \text{tr}(P) = N\}. \quad (2.2.19)$$

Note that the kinetic term can be written as

$$G_T^s[P] = -\frac{1}{2} \operatorname{tr}(\Delta_r P) \quad (2.2.20)$$

and the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian Eq. (2.2.12) is just the variation of $G[P]$ with respect to the density operator P :

$$\nabla_P G[P] := \frac{\delta G[P]}{\delta P} = H[\rho]. \quad (2.2.21)$$

2.2.3 Kohn-Sham equations at finite temperature

The discussions above are all for the case of zero temperature. For finite temperature $T > 0$, instead of the energy $G[P]$ (or equivalently $F[\rho]$, $E[\psi]$), the quantum system will minimize the *free energy* instead, which can be defined conveniently using the density operator:

$$G_T[P] := G[P] + T \operatorname{tr}(s(P)), \quad (2.2.22)$$

where $s(\cdot)$ is the *electronic entropy* defined by

$$s(P) := P \log P + (I - P) \log(I - P) \quad (2.2.23)$$

and the optimization constraint (c.f. Eq. (2.2.19)) is replaced by

$$P \in \mathcal{M}_1 := \{P : L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}) \rightarrow L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}) \mid P = P^*, 0 \preceq P \preceq I, \operatorname{tr}(P) = N\}. \quad (2.2.24)$$

The notation $A \preceq B$ is defined by

$$A \preceq B \iff \langle \psi, A\psi \rangle \leq \langle \psi, B\psi \rangle, \quad \forall \psi \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}). \quad (2.2.25)$$

The Euler-Lagrange equation with ϵ_F (known as the *Fermi (energy) level*) as the Lagrange multiplier for the constraint $\operatorname{tr}(P) = N$ is given by

$$H[\rho] + T(\log P - \log(I - P)) - \epsilon_F I = 0. \quad (2.2.26)$$

Solving the above equation for P we get

$$P = \left(I + \exp\left(\frac{H[\rho] - \epsilon_F I}{T}\right) \right)^{-1} =: f_{\text{FD}}\left(\frac{H[\rho] - \epsilon_F I}{T}\right), \quad (2.2.27)$$

where f_T is called the *Fermi-Dirac mapping* or the (*Fermi-Dirac*) *smearing function* $f_{\text{FD}}(x) := 1/(1 + \exp(x))$. To get the Kohn-Sham equations, we need to reformulate the above equation as a nonlinear eigenvalue problem. Since the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian $H[\rho]$ is self-adjoint, we can write its spectral decomposition as

$$H[\rho] = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \epsilon_n \phi_n \otimes \phi_n, \quad (2.2.28)$$

and therefore

$$P = f_{\text{FD}} \left(\frac{H[\rho] - \epsilon_{\text{F}} I}{T} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \underbrace{f_{\text{FD}} \left(\frac{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{\text{F}}}{T} \right)}_{=: f_n} \phi_n \otimes \phi_n. \quad (2.2.29)$$

The constraint $P \in \mathcal{M}_1$ implies

$$0 \leq f_n \leq 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n = N. \quad (2.2.30)$$

Similar to the discussions in Eq. (2.2.15) and Eq. (2.2.16), we can obtain the kernel of the density operator and thus the diagonal part of the kernel being the electron density:

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2. \quad (2.2.31)$$

The constraint Eq. (2.2.30) implies that $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ is indeed an electron density, i.e., $\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{r}) \, d\mathbf{r} = N$. The real numbers $f_n \in [0, 1]$ are called the *occupation numbers*. For this reason, the smearing function $f_{\text{FD}}(x)$ is also called the *occupation function*. Conceptually, one can think of the occupation numbers as the probability of finding an electron in the n -th orbital. The orbitals ϕ_n with occupation number f_n larger than the Fermi level ϵ_{F} are called *occupied orbitals* and the others are called *unoccupied orbitals*. In summary, the Kohn-Sham equations at finite temperature are given by

$$\begin{aligned} H[\rho] \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) &= \epsilon_n \phi_n(\mathbf{r}), \quad \epsilon_1 \leq \epsilon_2 \leq \dots, \quad \langle \phi_n, \phi_m \rangle = \delta_{nm}, \\ \rho(\mathbf{r}) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2, \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n = N, \quad f_n = f_{\text{FD}} \left(\frac{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{\text{F}}}{T} \right), \\ H[\rho] &= -\frac{1}{2} \Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho](\mathbf{r}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.32)$$

Since f_{FD} is monotonically decreasing, the number of occupied orbitals is defined by $N_{\text{occ}} := \max\{n \in \mathbb{N} \mid f_n > \epsilon_{\text{F}}\}$.

Remark 2. Although there are infinitely many eigenfunctions of the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian $H[\rho]$, in practical DFT calculations, it is common to compute only the orbitals that are occupied by electrons, along with a limited number of unoccupied orbitals. Typically, this includes N_{ex} unoccupied orbitals, where $N_{\text{ex}} < N_{\text{occ}}$. See [36, 12, 13] for details for the self-consistent field (SCF) iteration for solving the Kohn-Sham equations.

Remark 3. When $T \rightarrow 0$, the Fermi-Dirac mapping f_{FD} converges to the step function

$$f_{\text{FD}}(x) \rightarrow \begin{cases} 1, & x \leq 0, \\ 0, & x > 0, \end{cases} \quad (2.2.33)$$

almost everywhere. In this case, $f_n = 1$ for $n \leq N_{\text{occ}}$ and $f_n = 0$ for $n > N_{\text{occ}}$. Therefore, the Kohn-Sham equations Eq. (2.2.32) is reduced to and consistent with the Kohn-Sham equations Eq. (2.2.10) at zero temperature. Hence, in the following discussions, we will only focus on the Kohn-Sham equations at finite temperature.

2.3 Density functional perturbation theory (DFPT)

Recall that in the Kohn-Sham equations Eq. (2.2.32), the Hartree-exchange-correlation potential $V_{\text{Hxc}}(\mathbf{r})$ is universal, which is the same for any system of N electrons, and depends on the electron density ρ . The external potential $V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})$, however, depends on the nuclear configuration of the system. Therefore, the solution of the Kohn-Sham equations defines a map from the external potential $V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})$ to the electron density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$:

$$\mathcal{F} : V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) \mapsto \rho(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.3.1)$$

The DFPT is interested in the derivative of this map with respect to the external potential $V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})$, i.e., the change of the electron density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ when the external potential $V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})$ is perturbed. This is useful in many applications, for example, the phonon calculations in solid state physics [7, 56]. In this section, we mostly follow the presentation in [11].

2.3.1 Dyson equation

To formulate the DFPT, we rewrite the Kohn-Sham equations in a more compact form by introducing the *potential to density Kohn-Sham map*

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{KS}} : V \mapsto \rho = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_{\text{FD}} \left(\frac{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{\text{F}}}{T} \right) |\phi_n|^2, \quad (2.3.2)$$

where $\{\phi_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ are orthonormal eigenfunctions of the operator $-\Delta_{\mathbf{r}} + V$ with corresponding eigenvalues $\{\epsilon_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ and ϵ_{F} is the unique real number such that the sum of the occupation numbers is N . Then by definition, the Kohn-Sham equations can be written as the fixed point equation for ρ :

$$\rho = \mathcal{F}_{\text{KS}} (V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]). \quad (2.3.3)$$

We remark that the Kohn-Sham map \mathcal{F}_{KS} is not just a shift of the external potential to density map \mathcal{F} defined in Eq. (2.3.1): \mathcal{F} is defined by the solution ρ of the above implicit equation for a given external potential $V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})$. Taking the derivative of the Kohn-Sham map \mathcal{F}_{KS} with respect to the external potential $V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})$ we get

$$\frac{\delta \rho}{\delta V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})} = \underbrace{\mathcal{F}'_{\text{KS}}(V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho])}_{=:\chi_0} \left(I + \underbrace{\frac{\delta V_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]}{\delta \rho}}_{=:K_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]} \frac{\delta \rho}{\delta V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})} \right), \quad (2.3.4)$$

where χ_0 is called the *non-interacting susceptibility operator* and $K_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]$ is the *Hartree-exchange-correlation kernel*. Therefore, for an infinitesimal perturbation $\delta V_0(\mathbf{r})$ of the external potential, we get a first order approximation of the variation of the electron density, which is called the *Dyson*

equation:

$$\delta\rho = \chi_0 (\delta V_0 + K_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]\delta\rho) \iff (1 - \chi_0 K_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]) \delta\rho = \chi_0 \delta V_0. \quad (2.3.5)$$

$\mathcal{E} := 1 - \chi_0 K_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]$ is called the *dielectric operator*. The calculation of the Hartree-exchange-correlation kernel $K_{\text{Hxc}}[\rho]$ is standard and well-established [60, 33]. We only focus on the application of the non-interacting susceptibility operator χ_0 in this thesis.

2.3.2 Application of the non-interacting susceptibility operator

For a given external potential perturbation $\delta V(\mathbf{r})$, it can be shown [7, 14] that the application of the non-interacting susceptibility operator χ_0 is given by

$$\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{f_n - f_m}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m} \phi_n^*(\mathbf{r}) \phi_m(\mathbf{r}) (\delta V_{mn} - \delta\epsilon_{\text{F}} \delta_{mn}), \quad (2.3.6)$$

where $\delta\epsilon_{\text{F}}$ is the induced variation of the Fermi level due to the perturbation $\delta V(\mathbf{r})$, $\delta V_{mn} := \langle \phi_m, \delta V \phi_n \rangle$ and we use the convention that

$$\frac{f_n - f_m}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m} := \lim_{\epsilon_n \rightarrow \epsilon_m} f_{\text{FD}} \left(\frac{\epsilon - \epsilon_{\text{F}}}{T} \right) = \frac{1}{T} f'_{\text{FD}} \left(\frac{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{\text{F}}}{T} \right) =: f'_n. \quad (2.3.7)$$

We note that the number of electrons is conserved (termed *charge conservation*) under the perturbation and the orbitals ϕ_n are orthonormal, which implies that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \delta\rho(\mathbf{r}) \, d\mathbf{r} = 0 \implies \delta\epsilon_{\text{F}} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f'_n \delta\epsilon_n}{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f'_n}, \quad (2.3.8)$$

where $\delta\epsilon_n := \delta V_{nn} = \langle \phi_n, \delta V \phi_n \rangle$.

2.3.3 Practical computation of the non-interacting susceptibility operator

As we mentioned in Remark 2, in practice, we only compute $N_{\text{occ}} + N_{\text{ex}}$ orbitals. Therefore, the infinite sum Eq. (2.3.6) is not usable in practical computations. Instead, we start from the truncated electron density

$$\rho_{N_{\text{occ}}}(\mathbf{r}) := \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} f_n |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 \quad (2.3.9)$$

and differentiating it yields

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\rho_{N_{\text{occ}}}(\mathbf{r}) &= \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} f_n (\phi_n^*(\mathbf{r})\delta\phi_n(\mathbf{r}) + \delta\phi_n^*(\mathbf{r})\phi_n(\mathbf{r})) + \delta f_n |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \text{Re}(\phi_n^*(\mathbf{r})\delta\phi_n(\mathbf{r})) + \delta f_n |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2.\end{aligned}\tag{2.3.10}$$

Since the variation of the orbital $\delta\phi_n(\mathbf{r})$ is still in the Hilbert space $L^2(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C})$, we can expand it to linear combinations of the orbitals. Let P be the orthogonal projection operator onto the occupied subspace $\text{span}\{\phi_n\}_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}}$ and Q be the orthogonal projection operator onto the unoccupied subspace $\text{span}\{\phi_n\}_{n=N_{\text{occ}}+1}^{\infty}$. Then

$$P = \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \phi_n \otimes \phi_n \quad \text{and} \quad Q = I - P = \sum_{n=N_{\text{occ}}+1}^{\infty} \phi_n \otimes \phi_n.\tag{2.3.11}$$

Let $\delta\phi_n^P := P\delta\phi_n$ and $\delta\phi_n^Q := Q\delta\phi_n$, we have

$$f_n\delta\phi_n = f_n\delta\phi_n^P + f_n\delta\phi_n^Q = \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \underbrace{\langle \phi_m, f_n\delta\phi_n \rangle}_{=: \Gamma_{mn}} \phi_m + f_n\delta\phi_n^Q, \quad n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}.\tag{2.3.12}$$

Plugging Eq. (2.3.12) into Eq. (2.3.10) we get

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\rho_{N_{\text{occ}}}(\mathbf{r}) &= \sum_{n,m=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} (\Gamma_{mn} + \Gamma_{nm}^*) \phi_n^*(\mathbf{r})\phi_m(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \text{Re}(\phi_n^*(\mathbf{r})\delta\phi_n^Q(\mathbf{r})) + \delta f_n |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} (2\text{Re}(\Gamma_{nn}) + \delta f_n) |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 + \sum_{1 \leq m \neq n \leq N_{\text{occ}}} (\Gamma_{mn} + \Gamma_{mn}^*) \phi_n^*(\mathbf{r})\phi_m(\mathbf{r}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \text{Re}(\phi_n^*(\mathbf{r})\delta\phi_n^Q(\mathbf{r})).\end{aligned}\tag{2.3.13}$$

In order to compute Γ_{mn} , $\delta\phi_n^Q$ and δf_n , we first note by the charge conservation again that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \delta\rho_{N_{\text{occ}}}(\mathbf{r}) \, d\mathbf{r} = 0 \implies \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2\text{Re}(\Gamma_{nn}) + \delta f_n = 0.\tag{2.3.14}$$

Then, since $\delta\rho_{N_{\text{occ}}}(\mathbf{r})$ needs to be able to represent $\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})$ in Eq. (2.3.6) accurately, they need to coincide with each other at least approximately. We first rewrite Eq. (2.3.6) as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\rho(\mathbf{r}) \approx & \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} f'_n |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 (\delta\epsilon_n - \delta\epsilon_{\text{F}}) + \sum_{1 \leq m \neq n \leq N_{\text{occ}}} \frac{f_n - f_m}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m} \phi_n^*(\mathbf{r}) \phi_m(\mathbf{r}) \delta V_{mn} \\ & + \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \sum_{m=N_{\text{occ}}+1}^{\infty} 2 \frac{f_n}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m} \text{Re}(\phi_n^*(\mathbf{r}) \phi_m(\mathbf{r}) \delta V_{mn}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.15)$$

where we neglected the terms with $f_n, f_m, n, m > N_{\text{occ}}$ since they are small. Performing a term by term comparison between Eq. (2.3.15) and Eq. (2.3.10), we get that the first terms coincide with each other and therefore

$$2 \text{Re}(\Gamma_{nn}) + \delta f_n = f'_n (\delta\epsilon_n - \delta\epsilon_{\text{F}}), \quad n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}. \quad (2.3.16)$$

Similarly, for the second term, we get

$$\Gamma_{mn} + \Gamma_{mn}^* = \frac{f_n - f_m}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m} \delta V_{mn} := \Delta_{mn}, \quad 1 \leq m \neq n \leq N_{\text{occ}}, \quad (2.3.17)$$

and for the third term, we have

$$\delta\phi_n^Q(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{m=N_{\text{occ}}+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m} \phi_m(\mathbf{r}) \delta V_{mn}, \quad n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}. \quad (2.3.18)$$

Recall that by the spectral decomposition of the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian $H[\rho]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\epsilon_n - H[\rho]) \delta\phi_n^Q(\mathbf{r}) &= \left(\sum_{m'=1}^{\infty} (\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{m'}) \phi_{m'}(\mathbf{r}) \otimes \phi_{m'}(\mathbf{r}) \right) \delta\phi_n^Q \\ &= \sum_{m=N_{\text{occ}}+1}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=1}^{\infty} \frac{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{m'}}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m} \phi_{m'}(\mathbf{r}) \langle \phi_m, \phi_{m'} \rangle \delta V_{mn} \\ &= \sum_{m=N_{\text{occ}}+1}^{\infty} \phi_m(\mathbf{r}) \delta V_{mn} = \sum_{m=N_{\text{occ}}+1}^{\infty} \phi_m(\mathbf{r}) \langle \phi_m, \delta V \phi_n \rangle \\ &= Q(\delta V \phi_n), \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.19)$$

i.e., $\delta\phi_n^Q(\mathbf{r})$ is a solution to the above equation. We further notice that $\delta\phi_n^Q(\mathbf{r})$ is in the range of Q and therefore, $\delta\phi_n^Q$ is the unique solution to the so-called *Sternheimer equation* [54]:

$$Q(\epsilon_n - H[\rho]) Q \delta\phi_n^Q = Q(\delta V \phi_n). \quad (2.3.20)$$

We note that the equations Eqs. (2.3.14), (2.3.16) and (2.3.17) still cannot determine δf_n and Γ_{mn} uniquely. This is not because of we missed something but because of the unitary invariance of the Kohn-Sham equations as discussed in the beginning of Section 2.2.2, i.e., there is no unique choice of the orbitals. Therefore, we need to introduce some additional constraints, which are called the *gauge*

conditions, to fix the degrees of freedom. A first gauge choice is that $\Gamma_{nn} = 0$ for $n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}$, which gives the formula for δf_n :

$$\delta f_n = f'_n (\delta \epsilon_n - \delta \epsilon_{\text{F}}), \quad n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}. \quad (2.3.21)$$

Note that the charge conservation condition Eq. (2.3.14) is not destroyed and is automatically satisfied due to Eq. (2.3.8). As for Γ_{mn} 's, there are multiple choices in literature [7, 11] and software packages [26, 19, 22] that lead to (different) uniquely defined Γ_{mn} 's and we will not discuss them in details here. With some additional gauge choice $g : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, we can define Γ_{mn} uniquely by

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{nn} &= 0, \quad n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}, \\ \Gamma_{mn} + \Gamma_{mn}^* &= \Delta_{mn}, \quad g(\Gamma_{mn}) = 0, \quad 1 \leq m \neq n \leq N_{\text{occ}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.22)$$

In summary, combining Eqs. (2.3.10), (2.3.12) and (2.3.20) to (2.3.22), the application of the non-interacting susceptibility operator $\delta \rho = \chi_0 \delta V$ can be computed by

$$\delta \rho = \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \text{Re} (\phi_n^* (\delta \phi_n^P + \delta \phi_n^Q)) + \delta f_n |\phi_n|^2, \quad (2.3.23)$$

where for $n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta f_n &= f'_n (\delta \epsilon_n - \delta \epsilon_{\text{F}}), \\ \delta \phi_n^P &= \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \Gamma_{mn} \phi_m, \quad \Gamma_{mn} \text{ satisfies Eq. (2.3.22),} \\ \delta \phi_n^Q &\text{ solves the Sternheimer equation Eq. (2.3.20).} \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.24)$$

2.4 Numerical discretization

In order to solve the Kohn-Sham DFT or DFPT in practice, the continuous equations need to be discretized. In this section, we will discuss the plane-wave discretization [32, 44], also known as the Fourier basis method or the pseudospectral method, which is the most popular discretization scheme in practice. We refer the readers to [36] for more details of other discretization schemes and [10] for the numerical analysis of plane-wave discretization of the Kohn-Sham DFT.

2.4.1 Plane-wave basis

Up to now, we have only discussed the Kohn-Sham equations for *isolated systems* where the effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})$ decays to zero as $|\mathbf{r}| \rightarrow \infty$. In practice, another important class of systems is *condensed matter systems* such as liquids and solids, where the effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})$ is supported on the macroscopic scale and can therefore be considered to be infinity from the

microscopic perspective [35, Section 1.4]. In this case, the effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})$ is periodic with respect to some *periodic lattice*. Formally, consider a *simulation cell* or the so-called *unitcell*

$$\Omega = [0, 1)\mathbf{a}_1 + [0, 1)\mathbf{a}_2 + [0, 1)\mathbf{a}_3 = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^3 c_i \mathbf{a}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid c_i \in [0, 1) \right\}, \quad (2.4.1)$$

for some (non-necessarily orthonormal) linear independent vectors $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3 \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The *periodic lattice* is defined by

$$\mathbb{L} = \left\{ \mathbf{R} = \sum_{i=1}^3 n_i \mathbf{a}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid n_i \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}. \quad (2.4.2)$$

Then the effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})$ is periodic with respect to the periodic lattice \mathbb{L} (termed \mathbb{L} -*periodic*), i.e.,

$$V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{R}) = V_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}), \quad \forall \mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{L}. \quad (2.4.3)$$

We denote the space of locally square integrable \mathbb{L} -periodic functions by

$$L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C}) := \left\{ u : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \mid u(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{R}) = u(\mathbf{r}), \forall \mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{L}, \int_{\Omega} |u(\mathbf{r})|^2 d\mathbf{r} < \infty \right\}. \quad (2.4.4)$$

In this case, the main unknown functions in the Kohn-Sham equations, i.e., the orbitals $\phi_n(\mathbf{r})$'s and the electron density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$, are also \mathbb{L} -periodic. Therefore, they can be expanded in the Fourier series

$$u(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{L}^*} \widehat{[u]}_{\mathbf{G}} e_{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.4.5)$$

where the lattice \mathbb{L}^* is defined by

$$\mathbb{L}^* = \left\{ \mathbf{G} = \sum_{i=1}^3 m_i \mathbf{b}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid m_i \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{b}_i \cdot \mathbf{a}_j = 2\pi \delta_{ij}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3 \quad (2.4.6)$$

and the Fourier basis functions $e_{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r})$'s are defined by

$$e_{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|\Omega|}} e^{i\mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \quad \mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{L}^*. \quad (2.4.7)$$

Here $|\Omega|$ is the volume of the unitcell Ω . It is easy to verify that the Fourier basis functions $e_{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r})$'s are \mathbb{L} -periodic and orthonormal, which justifies the choice to expand the orbitals and the electron density in the Fourier series Eq. (2.4.5). The Fourier coefficients $\widehat{[u]}_{\mathbf{G}}$'s are then given by

$$\widehat{[u]}_{\mathbf{G}} = \langle e_{\mathbf{G}}, u \rangle_{L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{C})} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|\Omega|}} \int_{\Omega} u(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{r}} d\mathbf{r}. \quad (2.4.8)$$

The lattice \mathbb{L}^* is called the *reciprocal lattice* of \mathbb{L} and the vectors \mathbf{G} in \mathbb{L}^* are called the *wave vectors*. The Fourier basis functions $e_{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r})$'s are also called the *plane-wave basis functions* or simply *plane-waves*.

2.4.2 Plane-wave discretization

This section is based on a recent presentation by Eric Cancès [9]. We consider a finite subset of the plane-waves

$$\mathcal{X}_{E_{\text{cut}}}^{\circ} := \text{span}\{e_{\mathbf{G}} \mid \mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{G}_{E_{\text{cut}}}^{\circ}\}, \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbb{G}_{E_{\text{cut}}}^{\circ} := \left\{ \mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{L}^* \mid |\mathbf{G}| \leq \sqrt{2E_{\text{cut}}} \right\}, \quad (2.4.9)$$

where $E_{\text{cut}} > 0$ is a user-defined parameter called the *cut-off energy* and we use the superscript \circ since the set $\mathbb{G}_{E_{\text{cut}}}^{\circ}$ is the intersection of the ball of radius $\sqrt{2E_{\text{cut}}}$ centered at the origin with the reciprocal lattice \mathbb{L}^* . We may drop the subscript E_{cut} when it is clear from the context. Then the dimension of \mathcal{X}° is

$$N_{\text{b}} := \dim \mathcal{X}^{\circ} = |\mathbb{G}^{\circ}| = C_{\text{d}} \frac{4\pi}{3} \left(\sqrt{2E_{\text{cut}}} \right)^3 = C_{\text{d}} \frac{8\sqrt{2}\pi}{3} E_{\text{cut}}^{3/2}, \quad (2.4.10)$$

where C_{d} is the (average) number of lattice points per unit volume in the reciprocal lattice \mathbb{L}^* . The orbitals $\phi_n(\mathbf{r})$'s are discretized in this finite-dimensional subspace, i.e.,

$$\phi_n(\mathbf{r}) \approx \sum_{\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{G}^{\circ}} [\widehat{\phi}_n]_{\mathbf{G}} e_{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}) \in \mathcal{X}^{\circ}, \quad n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}. \quad (2.4.11)$$

The electron density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\mathbf{r}) &= \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} |\phi_n(\mathbf{r})|^2 \approx \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \sum_{\mathbf{G}, \mathbf{G}' \in \mathbb{G}^{\circ}} [\widehat{\phi}_n]_{\mathbf{G}}^* [\widehat{\phi}_n]_{\mathbf{G}'} e_{\mathbf{G}}^*(\mathbf{r}) e_{\mathbf{G}'}(\mathbf{r}) \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{G}^{\circ}} \underbrace{\left(|\Omega|^{-1/2} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \sum_{\mathbf{G}' \in \mathbb{G}^{\circ}} [\widehat{\phi}_n]_{\mathbf{G}}^* [\widehat{\phi}_n]_{\mathbf{G}+\mathbf{G}'} \right)}_{[\widehat{\rho}]_{\mathbf{G}}} e_{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.4.12)$$

Note that the Fourier coefficients includes wave vectors of the form $\mathbf{G} + \mathbf{G}'$, which are not necessarily in $\mathbb{G}^{\circ} = \mathbb{G}_{E_{\text{cut}}}^{\circ}$, but in $\mathbb{G}_{4E_{\text{cut}}}^{\circ}$. Therefore, for consistency, the density must be discretized on the larger plane-wave basis set:

$$\mathcal{X}^{\square} := \text{span}\{e_{\mathbf{G}} \mid \mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{G}^{\square}\}, \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbb{G}^{\square} := \left\{ \mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{L}^* \mid |\mathbf{G}|_{\infty} \leq 2\sqrt{2E_{\text{cut}}} \right\}, \quad (2.4.13)$$

where the superscript \square indicates that the set \mathbb{G}^{\square} is the intersection of the cube of side length $4\sqrt{2E_{\text{cut}}}$ centered at the origin with the reciprocal lattice \mathbb{L}^* . The dimension of \mathcal{X}^{\square} is

$$N_{\text{g}} := \dim \mathcal{X}^{\square} = |\mathbb{G}^{\square}| = C_{\text{d}} \left(4\sqrt{2E_{\text{cut}}} \right)^3 = C_{\text{d}} 128\sqrt{2} E_{\text{cut}}^{3/2} \approx 16N_{\text{b}}. \quad (2.4.14)$$

Note that both grids \mathbb{G}° and \mathbb{G}^\square are in the *Fourier frequency space*. We define another grid in the *real space* by

$$\mathbb{X} := \left\{ \frac{i_1}{\sqrt[3]{N_g}} \mathbf{a}_1 + \frac{i_2}{\sqrt[3]{N_g}} \mathbf{a}_2 + \frac{i_3}{\sqrt[3]{N_g}} \mathbf{a}_3 \mid 0 \leq i_1, i_2, i_3 < \sqrt[3]{N_g} \right\}, \quad (2.4.15)$$

where we assume that N_g is a perfect cube for simplicity. The cardinality of \mathbb{X} is then N_g . Therefore, for a function $u(\mathbf{r})$ defined on the unitcell Ω , we can transform its function values on \mathbb{X} , i.e., $[u(\mathbf{r})]_{\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{X}}$, to its Fourier coefficients $[\widehat{u}]_{\mathbf{G}}$ and vice versa by the *Fast Fourier Transform* (FFT) and its inverse (IFFT) respectively. Formally, we define the FFT and IFFT operators by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F} : \mathbb{C}^{N_g} &\rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{N_g}, & [u(\mathbf{r})]_{\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{X}} &\mapsto [\widehat{u}]_{\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{G}^\square}, \\ \mathbf{F}^{-1} : \mathbb{C}^{N_g} &\rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{N_g}, & [\widehat{u}]_{\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{G}^\square} &\mapsto [u(\mathbf{r})]_{\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{X}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.4.16)$$

Note that it is well-known that both operators are linear and they are unitary, i.e., $\mathbf{F}^{-1} = \mathbf{F}^*$. They are crucial for efficiently converting between function values in real space and their corresponding Fourier coefficients in reciprocal space.

Remark 4. We remark here that there are different normalization conventions for different software packages so that they are in fact unitary up to a constant. For the analysis in this thesis, we will not consider this setup and the arguments can be easily adapted.

2.4.3 Discretized Kohn-Sham equations

As we have seen, the orbitals $\phi_n(\mathbf{r})$'s and the electron density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ are discretized in the plane-wave basis set $\mathcal{X}_{E_{\text{cut}}}^\circ$ and \mathcal{X}^\square respectively. Let us introduce the following notations for their discretized objects. For orbitals $\phi_n(\mathbf{r})$'s, we use the bold font $\boldsymbol{\phi}_n \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b}$ to denote the discretized $\phi_n(\mathbf{r})$ in the *Fourier frequency space*, i.e., $\boldsymbol{\phi}_n$ contains the Fourier coefficients $[\widehat{\phi}_n]_{\mathbf{G}}$'s for $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{G}^\circ$. For the electron density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$, we use the bold font $\boldsymbol{\rho} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ to denote the discretized $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ in the *real space*, i.e., $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ contains the function values $[\rho(\mathbf{r})]_{\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{X}}$. We remark that in practical implementation, $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ may be further transformed to the Fourier frequency space to compute the potentials or some other intermediate quantities, but for simplicity and the purpose of this thesis, we just assume $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ is in the real space.

Given the above setup, if we have the discretized orbitals $\boldsymbol{\phi}_n \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b}$, in order to compute the discretized electron density $\boldsymbol{\rho} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$, we first perform a zero padding on $\boldsymbol{\phi}_n$ to get a vector $\boldsymbol{\phi}_n^\square \in \mathbb{C}^{N_g}$, i.e., we add 0's for Fourier coefficients in $\mathbb{G}^\square \setminus \mathbb{G}^\circ$, and then apply in inverse FFT \mathbf{F}^{-1} to get the function values $[\phi_n^\square(\mathbf{r})]_{\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{X}}$ on the real space grid \mathbb{X} . Finally, we compute the electron density $\boldsymbol{\rho} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ in the real space by Eq. (2.3.9). In matrix form, this procedure can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\rho} = \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} f_n |\mathbf{F}^{-1} \mathbf{Z} \boldsymbol{\phi}_n|^2, \quad (2.4.17)$$

where $|\cdot|^2$ is the component-wise square of a vector and $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_b}$ is the *zero-padding matrix*, which is a sparse matrix with only 0 and 1. We denote $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{F}^{-1} \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_b}$. For the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian $H[\rho]$, we skip the details and claim that given a discretized electron density $\rho \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$, the discretized Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian $\mathbf{H}[\rho]$ is a Hermitian matrix in $\mathbb{C}^{N_b \times N_b}$. In summary, the discretized Kohn-Sham equations (c.f. Eq. (2.2.32)) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}[\rho] \phi_n &= \epsilon_n \phi_n, \quad n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}, \quad \langle \phi_n, \phi_m \rangle = \delta_{nm}, \\ \rho &= \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} f_n |\mathbf{S} \phi_n|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2.4.18)$$

which is a non-linear eigenvalue problem and can be solved by the *self-consistent field* (SCF) iteration, see [36, 12, 13] for details. This gives us $N_{\text{occ}} + N_{\text{ex}}$ eigenpairs

$$(\phi_n, \epsilon_n) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b} \times \mathbb{R} \quad \text{for } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}} + N_{\text{ex}}, \quad (2.4.19)$$

where the first N_{occ} eigenpairs are occupied and the last N_{ex} eigenpairs are unoccupied. With those eigenpairs, we can determine the electron density ρ and then the Hamiltonian matrix $\mathbf{H}[\rho]$ and the occupation numbers f_n 's.

2.4.4 Discretized Dyson equation

With the discretized Kohn-Sham equations solved and all these quantities at hand, we can write down the discretized Dyson equation in the real space as (c.f. Eq. (2.3.5))

$$\text{Seek } \delta \rho \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g} \text{ such that } , (\mathbf{I}_{N_g} - \chi_0 \mathbf{K}) \delta \rho = \delta \rho_0, \quad (2.4.20)$$

where $\chi_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_g}$ is the discretized non-interacting susceptibility operator and $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_g}$ is the discretized Hartree-exchange-correlation kernel. Let $\mathcal{E} := \mathbf{I}_{N_g} - \chi_0 \mathbf{K}$ be the discretized dielectric operator. The right-hand side $\delta \rho_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ is the discretized initial perturbation of the electron density. By similar procedures as for deriving Eq. (2.4.17), the application of $\chi_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_g}$ on a discretized potential $\delta \mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ in the real space can be computed by (c.f. Eq. (2.3.23))

$$\delta \rho = \chi_0 \delta \mathbf{V} = \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \text{Re}((\mathbf{S} \phi_n)^* \cdot (\mathbf{S} \delta \phi_n^P + \mathbf{S} \delta \phi_n^Q)) + \delta f_n |\mathbf{S} \phi_n|^2, \quad (2.4.21)$$

where for $n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta f_n &= f'_n (\delta \epsilon_n - \delta \epsilon_F), \\ \delta \phi_n^P &= \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \Gamma_{mn} \phi_m, \quad \Gamma_{mn} \text{ satisfies Eq. (2.3.22)}, \\ \delta \phi_n^Q &\text{ solves } \mathbf{Q} (\mathbf{H}[\rho] - \epsilon_n \mathbf{I}_{N_b}) \mathbf{Q} \delta \phi_n^Q = -\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{S}^* (\delta \mathbf{V} \cdot (\mathbf{S} \phi_n)). \end{aligned} \quad (2.4.22)$$

We conclude this chapter by making some remarks on the above equations.

Remark 5. 1. The operations Re , \cdot , $*$ and $|\cdot|^2$ in Eq. (2.4.21) should be understood component-wise.

2. $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_b \times N_b}$ is the orthogonal projection onto the subspace spanned by $\{\phi_n\}_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}}$, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I}_{N_b} - \mathbf{\Phi}\mathbf{\Phi}^\top, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{\Phi} = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_{N_{\text{occ}}}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b \times N_{\text{occ}}}. \quad (2.4.23)$$

3. $\mathbf{S}^* = \mathbf{Z}^\top \mathbf{F}$, where $\mathbf{Z}^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{N_b \times N_g}$ denotes the transpose of the zero-padding matrix $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_b}$, which is a restriction operator from the larger Fourier frequency space \mathbb{G}^\square to the smaller one \mathbb{G}° . The right hand side of the discretized Sternheimer equation admits this form since $\delta \mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ is in the real space. So we first transform the orbital $\phi_n \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b}$ to the real space, then apply the potential and finally transform back to the Fourier frequency space.

4. Recall that $N_g \approx 16N_b$. Therefore, the discretized Dyson equation is a large $N_g \times N_g$ *real non-symmetric* linear system while the discretized Sternheimer equation is a *complex Hermitian* linear system with a smaller size $N_b \times N_b$. In practice, we do not form the Hamiltonian $\mathbf{H}[\rho]$ and \mathcal{E} explicitly and only access them through matrix-vector products, which can be computed efficiently by FFT. In such a case, direct methods are not applicable and iterative methods are needed to solve the linear systems. We solve the discretized Dyson equation by the generalized minimal residual (GMRES) method [52] and the discretized Sternheimer equation by the conjugate gradient (CG) method [27]. We will discuss the details in the next chapter.

Chapter 3

An Inexact Krylov Subspace Method

In this chapter, we introduce the inexact GMRES method [53, 58], which computes the matrix-vector product inexactly. We first briefly introduce the basics of Krylov subspace methods and then discuss the standard GMRES method. We refer the readers to the standard textbooks of iterative solver, e.g., [51, 57], for more details. Finally, we introduce the inexact GMRES method and discuss its convergence properties. It is important to note that the symbols in this chapter parallel those in Chapter 2 and do not represent any physical quantities unless otherwise stated.

3.1 Krylov subspace methods

Given a linear system

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}, \quad \mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{C}^n, \quad (3.1.1)$$

and an initial guess $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{C}^n$ of the solution, a number of popular iterative methods extract an approximation to the solution of Eq. (3.1.1) from the *Krylov subspace* $\mathcal{K}_m(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$, which is defined by

$$\mathcal{K}_m(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0) := \text{span}\{\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{A}^2\mathbf{r}_0, \dots, \mathbf{A}^{m-1}\mathbf{r}_0\}. \quad (3.1.2)$$

Here $\mathbf{r}_0 := \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_0$ is the initial residual. The Krylov subspace methods are usually used to solve large linear systems where the matrix \mathbf{A} is not stored explicitly and only the matrix-vector product $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}$ can be computed for any given vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{C}^n$.

3.1.1 Arnoldi process

To work with the m -dimensional Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_m(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$, we need to have a basis for it. The most natural choice

$$\{\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{A}^2\mathbf{r}_0, \dots, \mathbf{A}^{m-1}\mathbf{r}_0\} \quad (3.1.3)$$

is numerically badly behaved. Because of the convergence of the power method, the vectors of this basis tend to lie in the same direction, making the basis useless in finite precision arithmetic. For similar reasons, the Gram-Schmidt process applied to this basis is also numerically unstable. The following simple lemma allows us to avoid explicit computation of $\mathbf{A}^k \mathbf{r}_0$'s.

Lemma 3.1.1. *If $\{\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_k\}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{K}_k(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$ for any $k \leq m$, then*

$$\{\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_m, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}_m\} \quad (3.1.4)$$

is a basis for $\mathcal{K}_{m+1}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$.

The proof, being direct and based on standard linear algebraic principles, is omitted for brevity. Given an orthonormal basis $\mathbf{V}_m = [\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_m] \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times m}$ for $\mathcal{K}_m(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$, Lemma 3.1.1 suggests that we can construct an orthonormal basis $\mathbf{V}_{m+1} = [\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{m+1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times (m+1)}$ for $\mathcal{K}_{m+1}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$ by first adding $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}_m$ to the basis \mathbf{V}_m and then applying one step of the (Classical) Gram-Schmidt (CGS) process to the resulting basis. This leads to Algorithm 1, the *Arnoldi process*.

Algorithm 1 Arnoldi process

Require: $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, $\mathbf{r}_0 \in \mathbb{C}^n$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$

Ensure: An orthonormal basis \mathbf{V}_{m+1} for $\mathcal{K}_{m+1}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$

- 1: $\beta = \|\mathbf{r}_0\|$, $\mathbf{v}_1 = \mathbf{r}_0/\beta$
 - 2: $\mathbf{V}_1 = \mathbf{v}_1$
 - 3: **for** $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$ **do**
 - 4: $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}_k$
 - 5: $\mathbf{h}_k = \mathbf{V}_k^* \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^k$
 - 6: $\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{h}_k$
 - 7: $h_{k+1,k} = \|\mathbf{v}_{k+1}\|$
 - 8: $\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{v}_{k+1}/h_{k+1,k}$
 - 9: $\mathbf{V}_{k+1} = [\mathbf{V}_k, \mathbf{v}_{k+1}]$
-

It is useful to store the coefficients \mathbf{h}_k 's and $h_{k+1,k}$'s in a matrix. Let h_{jk} be the j -th entry of \mathbf{h}_k for $j = 1, \dots, k$, then the matrix $\mathbf{H}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{(m+1) \times m}$ defined by

$$\mathbf{H}_m = \begin{bmatrix} h_{11} & h_{12} & \cdots & h_{1m} \\ h_{21} & h_{22} & \ddots & \vdots \\ & \ddots & \ddots & h_{m-1,m} \\ & & h_{m,m-1} & h_{mm} \\ & & & h_{m+1,m} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.1.5)$$

is called the (*upper*) *Hessenberg matrix* and has zero entries below the first subdiagonal. Note that Lines 4 to 8 in Algorithm 1 can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}_k = \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{h}_k + h_{k+1,k} \mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{V}_{k+1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{h}_k \\ h_{k+1,k} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{for } k = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (3.1.6)$$

which leads to the so-called *Arnoldi decomposition*:

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}_m = \mathbf{V}_{m+1}\mathbf{H}_m. \quad (3.1.7)$$

3.1.2 Generalized minimal residual method (GMRES)

The *generalized minimal residual method* (GMRES) seeks an approximate solution $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{C}^n$ of Eq. (3.1.1) in the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$ such that the norm of the residual $\mathbf{r}_k := \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_k$ is minimized. For this purpose, we first construct an orthonormal basis \mathbf{V}_k for $\mathcal{K}_k(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$ by the Arnoldi process. Then we suppose the approximate solution \mathbf{x}_k is in $\mathbf{x}_0 + \mathcal{K}_k(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{V}_k\mathbf{y}_k, \quad \text{for some } \mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{C}^k. \quad (3.1.8)$$

Then the norm of the residual \mathbf{r}_k is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{r}_k\| &= \|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_k\| = \|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}_k\mathbf{y}_k\| = \|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{V}_{k+1}\mathbf{H}_k\mathbf{y}_k\| \\ &= \|\mathbf{V}_{k+1}(\beta\mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_k\mathbf{y}_k)\| = \|\beta\mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_k\mathbf{y}_k\|, \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.9)$$

where we used the Arnoldi decomposition Eq. (3.1.7), the fact that \mathbf{V}_{k+1} has orthonormal columns and the convention that $\beta = \|\mathbf{r}_0\|$ and \mathbf{e}_1 is the first column of the conformable identity matrix. Let us denote

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k := \beta\mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_k\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{k+1}, \quad (3.1.10)$$

then the *true residual* \mathbf{r}_k is minimized if and only if the *estimated residual* $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k$ is minimized. Therefore, the GMRES method only solves a $(k+1) \times k$ least squares problem for \mathbf{y}_k in each iteration of the Arnoldi process and monitors the norm of the estimated residual $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$ to check the convergence. In fact, it turns out that we even do not need to solve the least squares problem explicitly and we can construct the solutions \mathbf{y}_k iteratively. From now on, let us denote \mathbf{y}_k by the solution of the least squares problem in the k -th iteration, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{y}_k := \arg \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^k} \|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\| = \arg \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^k} \|\beta\mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_k\mathbf{y}\|. \quad (3.1.11)$$

Theorem 3.1.2. *Let $\mathbf{h}^k \in \mathbb{C}^k$ be the conjugate transpose of the first row of the Hessenberg matrix $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{(k+1) \times k}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{k \times k}$ be the upper triangular matrix obtained by removing the first row from \mathbf{H}_k . Let us define $\mathbf{u}_k := \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-*}\mathbf{h}^k \in \mathbb{C}^k$. If $h_{k+1,k} \neq 0$, then the solution $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{C}^k$ of the least squares problem can be written as*

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \frac{\beta}{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2} \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-1}\mathbf{u}_k, \quad (3.1.12)$$

and the estimated residual norm is given by

$$\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\| = \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2}}. \quad (3.1.13)$$

Proof. By the normal equation of the least squares problem Eq. (3.1.11) and the Sherman–Morrison formula we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{y}_k &= \beta (\mathbf{H}_k^* \mathbf{H}_k)^{-1} \mathbf{H}_k^* \mathbf{e}_1 = \beta \left(\mathbf{h}^k (\mathbf{h}^k)^* + \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^* \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k \right)^{-1} \mathbf{h}^k \\
&= \beta \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-*} \mathbf{h}^k - \frac{\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-*} \mathbf{h}^k (\mathbf{h}^k)^* \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-*} \mathbf{h}^k}{1 + (\mathbf{h}^k)^* \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-*} \mathbf{h}^k} \right) \\
&= \frac{\beta}{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2} \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-1} \mathbf{u}_k.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1.14}$$

Therefore, the estimated residual norm is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\| &= \|\beta \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{y}_k\| = \left\| \beta \mathbf{e}_1 - \frac{\beta}{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2} \begin{bmatrix} \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 \\ \mathbf{u}_k \end{bmatrix} \right\| \\
&= \frac{\beta}{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2} \left\| \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -\mathbf{u}_k \end{bmatrix} \right\| = \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1.15}$$

□

We can see that both the solution \mathbf{y}_k and the estimated residual norm $\|\widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$ depends on the key quantity \mathbf{u}_k , which can be computed iteratively due to the fact that $\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k$ is upper triangular. In fact, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{u}_{k+1} &= \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_{k+1}^{-*} \mathbf{h}^{k+1} = \begin{bmatrix} \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k & \mathbf{h}_{2:k+1,k+1} \\ \mathbf{0} & h_{k+2,k+1} \end{bmatrix}^{-*} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{h}^k \\ h_{1,k+1}^* \end{bmatrix} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-*} & \mathbf{0} \\ -h_{k+2,k+1}^{-*} \mathbf{h}_{2:k+1,k+1}^* \widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^{-*} & h_{k+2,k+1}^{-*} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{h}^k \\ h_{1,k+1}^* \end{bmatrix} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_k \\ -h_{k+2,k+1}^{-*} \mathbf{h}_{2:k+1,k+1}^* \mathbf{u}_k + h_{k+2,k+1}^{-*} h_{1,k+1}^* \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1.16}$$

In other words, \mathbf{u}_{k+1} can be computed from \mathbf{u}_k by appending one entry. In summary, the GMRES method is formally described in Algorithm 2. Note that we do not compute \mathbf{y}_k explicitly until the estimated residual norm $\|\widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$, which is the same as the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|$, is smaller than a given tolerance $\tau > 0$.

Algorithm 2 GMRES

Require: Matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, right hand side $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, initial guess $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{C}^n$, maximum number of iterations $m \in \mathbb{N}$, tolerance $\tau > 0$

Ensure: An approximate solution \mathbf{x} with $\|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}\| \leq \tau$

```
1:  $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_0$ 
2:  $\beta = \|\mathbf{r}_0\|$ ,  $\mathbf{v}_1 = \mathbf{r}_0/\beta$ 
3:  $\mathbf{V}_1 = \mathbf{v}_1$ 
4: for  $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$  do
5:    $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}_k$ 
6:    $\mathbf{h}_k = \mathbf{V}_k^* \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^k$ 
7:    $\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{h}_k$ 
8:    $h_{k+1,k} = \|\mathbf{v}_{k+1}\|$ 
9:    $\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{v}_{k+1}/h_{k+1,k}$ 
10:   $\mathbf{V}_{k+1} = [\mathbf{V}_k, \mathbf{v}_{k+1}]$ 
11:  Compute  $\mathbf{u}_k$  iteratively by Eq. (3.1.16) (or if  $k = 1$ ,  $\mathbf{u}_1 = h_{11}^*/h_{21}^-$ )
12:  Compute the estimated residual norm  $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$  by Eq. (3.1.13)
13:  if  $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\| \leq \tau$  then
14:    Compute  $\mathbf{y}_k$  by Eq. (3.1.12)
15:    return  $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{y}_k$ 
```

We conclude this section by making some remarks on the GMRES method.

- Remark 6.*
1. To improve numerical stability, it is necessary to use the modified Gram-Schmidt process instead of CGS in the Arnoldi process. See [38, Chapter 5.12.2] for numerical comparisons of these two variants of the GMRES.
 2. This implementation, first proposed in [2], is slightly cheaper than the standard one based on Givens rotations and is also conceptually simpler. To our best knowledge, the stability of this approach has not been studied theoretically. However, numerical experiments in [38, Chapter 5.12.2] show that this implementation is stable and slightly cheaper than the standard one.
 3. In Theorem 3.1.2, we assume that the GMRES method does not break down, i.e., $h_{k+1,k} \neq 0$. This is a reasonable assumption since the GMRES algorithm breaks down at the k -th step if and only if the approximate solution \mathbf{x}_k is exact [52, Proposition 6.10].
 4. The GMRES becomes expensive then m is large because of the Gram-Schmidt process and the storage of the Krylov basis. A straightforward remedy is to restart the GMRES method after m iterations, i.e., we set \mathbf{x}_0 to be the current approximate solution \mathbf{x}_k and go back to Line 1. We will adopt this strategy in our implementation. For more advanced restart strategies, see [4, 5] for instance.

3.1.3 Conjugate gradient method (CG)

Instead of minimizing the residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|$ in the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$, an alternative is to impose an orthogonality condition

$$\mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_k \perp \mathcal{K}_k(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0), \quad \text{for } \mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathcal{K}_k(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0), \quad (3.1.17)$$

which leads to the *full orthogonalization method* (FOM). In the special case of \mathbf{A} being Hermitian positive definite (HPD), the FOM is equivalent to the *conjugate gradient method* (CG). In this case, the Hessenberg matrix \mathbf{H}_k is tridiagonal and the CG method can be implemented in a very efficient three-term recurrence way. We skip the detailed yet elegant derivation of the CG method and only list the algorithm in Algorithm 3 for completeness. It is worth mentioning that, interestingly enough, although first proposed in [27] in the fifty's, it is only until the eighties that the CG method is first observed to be a Krylov subspace method [50].

Algorithm 3 CG

Require: HPD matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, right hand side $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, initial guess $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{C}^n$, maximum number of iterations $m \in \mathbb{N}$, tolerance $\tau > 0$

Ensure: An approximate solution \mathbf{x} with $\|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}\| \leq \tau$

```

1:  $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_0$ 
2:  $\mathbf{p}_0 = \mathbf{r}_0$ 
3: for  $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$  do
4:    $\alpha_k = \mathbf{r}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{r}_{k-1} / \mathbf{p}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{p}_{k-1}$ 
5:    $\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_{k-1}$ 
6:    $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{r}_{k-1} - \alpha_k \mathbf{A} \mathbf{p}_{k-1}$ 
7:   if  $\|\mathbf{r}_k\| \leq \tau$  then
8:     return  $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_k$ 
9:    $\beta_k = \mathbf{r}_k^* \mathbf{r}_k / \mathbf{r}_{k-1}^* \mathbf{r}_{k-1}$ 
10:   $\mathbf{p}_k = \mathbf{r}_k + \beta_k \mathbf{p}_{k-1}$ 

```

It is well known that CG converges exponentially in the \mathbf{A} -norm, see [57, Theorem 38.5] for instance. In fact, the convergence rate is characterized by the condition number of \mathbf{A} .

Theorem 3.1.3. *Let \mathbf{x}_k be the k -th iterate of the CG method Algorithm 3 and $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{b}$ be the exact solution of the linear system. Then we have*

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_k\|_{\mathbf{A}}}{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0\|_{\mathbf{A}}} \leq 2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\kappa(\mathbf{A})} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa(\mathbf{A})} + 1} \right)^k, \quad (3.1.18)$$

where $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = \|\mathbf{A}\| \|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\|$ is the condition number of \mathbf{A} and $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbf{A}}$ is defined by $\|\mathbf{v}\|_{\mathbf{A}} := \sqrt{\mathbf{v}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v}}$.

Note that the residual norm can be written as

$$\|\mathbf{r}_k\| = \|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_k\| = \|\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_k)\| \leq \|\mathbf{A}^{1/2}\| \|\mathbf{A}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_k)\| = \|\mathbf{A}^{1/2}\| \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_k\|_{\mathbf{A}}, \quad (3.1.19)$$

we get the following characterization of the convergence of CG in the residual norm.

Corollary 3.1.4. *Let \mathbf{r}_k be the k -th residual of the CG method Algorithm 3, then we have*

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{r}_k\|}{\|\mathbf{r}_0\|} \leq 2\sqrt{\kappa(\mathbf{A})} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\kappa(\mathbf{A})} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa(\mathbf{A})} + 1} \right)^k. \quad (3.1.20)$$

3.2 The inexact GMRES method

In many applications, the matrix-vector product $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}$ is often performed approximately rather than exactly, either because of the expensiveness of the matrix-vector product or because the exact matrix-vector product is not even available. In this case, the exact matrix-vector product $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}$ is replaced by an inexact one $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{v}$ with

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} := \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{E}, \quad (3.2.1)$$

for some perturbation or error matrix $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$. In the context of the GMRES method, the matrix-vector product in Line 4 of Algorithm 1 is replaced by

$$\mathbf{w} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(k)}\mathbf{v}_k = (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{E}_k)\mathbf{v}_k, \quad (3.2.2)$$

for some error matrix $\mathbf{E}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$, which leads to the inexact Arnoldi decomposition

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}_m + [\mathbf{E}_1\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{E}_2\mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{E}_m\mathbf{v}_m] = \mathbf{V}_{m+1}\mathbf{H}_m. \quad (3.2.3)$$

The initial residual \mathbf{r}_0 should also be computed inexactly by

$$\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{b} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(0)}\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{b} - (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{E}_0)\mathbf{x}_0. \quad (3.2.4)$$

Keeping other steps unchanged leads to the *inexact GMRES* method. However, note that in this case the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|$ does not match the estimated residual norm $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$ anymore and thus using the stopping criterion $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\| \leq \tau$ as Line 13 of Algorithm 2 may not guarantee that the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|$ to be larger than the requested tolerance τ . Therefore, it is necessary to carefully modify the stopping criterion to take into account any errors arising from the inexact matrix-vector product. In fact, the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_k\|$ and the estimated residual norm $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$ are related by the following lemma.

Lemma 3.2.1. *Let*

$$\mathbf{r}_m = \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_m, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_m = \beta\mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_m\mathbf{y}_m, \quad (3.2.5)$$

be the true residual and the estimated residual at the m -th iteration of the inexact GMRES method respectively, where \mathbf{y}_m is the solution of the least squares problem Eq. (3.1.11) and $\mathbf{x}_m = \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{V}_m\mathbf{y}_m$. Then we have

$$\|\mathbf{r}_m\| \leq \|\mathbf{E}_0\mathbf{x}_0\| + \|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_m\| + \sum_{k=1}^m \|\mathbf{E}_k\mathbf{v}_k\| |[\mathbf{y}_m]_k|, \quad (3.2.6)$$

where $[\mathbf{y}_m]_k$ is the k -th element of the vector \mathbf{y}_m for $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Proof. By Eq. (3.2.3) and Eq. (3.2.4) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_m &= \mathbf{E}_0 \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}_m \mathbf{y}_m = \mathbf{E}_0 \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{V}_{m+1} \mathbf{H}_m \mathbf{y}_m + [\mathbf{E}_1 \mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{E}_2 \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{E}_m \mathbf{v}_m] \mathbf{y}_m \\ &= \mathbf{E}_0 \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{V}_{m+1} (\beta \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_m \mathbf{y}_m) + [\mathbf{E}_1 \mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{E}_2 \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{E}_m \mathbf{v}_m] \mathbf{y}_m, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.7)$$

the result then follows from the triangle inequality. \square

We can see that in the case of inexact GMRES, if all the three terms of the right hand side of Eq. (3.2.6) are smaller than $\tau/3$, then the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_m\|$ is smaller than τ . In many applications (and also for our application to Dyson equation), we can control the error occurred in the inexact matrix-vector product $\|\mathbf{E}_k \mathbf{v}_k\|$ or $\|\mathbf{E}_0 \mathbf{x}_0\|$. Therefore, the only term that needed to be understood is the modulus of the k -th element of the solution to the least squares problem $|\mathbf{y}_m|_k$, which is given by the following lemma.

Lemma 3.2.2. *Let \mathbf{y}_m be the solution of the least squares problem Eq. (3.1.11), then we have*

$$|\mathbf{y}_m|_k \leq \min \left\{ \frac{1}{\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)}, \frac{1}{2\sigma_m(\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m)} \right\} \|\widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_{k-1}\|, \quad \text{for } k = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (3.2.8)$$

where $\sigma_m(\cdot)$ is the m -th singular value of a matrix sorted in descending order and we recall that $\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m$ is the upper triangular matrix obtained by removing the first row from \mathbf{H}_m defined in Theorem 3.1.2.

Proof. First, we note that

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathbf{y}_m]_k &= \mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{y}_m = \mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{H}_m^\dagger \beta \mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{H}_m^\dagger \beta \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{H}_m^\dagger \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{k-1} \mathbf{y}_{k-1} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{H}_m^\dagger \begin{bmatrix} \beta \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{H}_{k-1} \mathbf{y}_{k-1} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{H}_m^\dagger \begin{bmatrix} \widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_{k-1} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.9)$$

therefore

$$|\mathbf{y}_m|_k \leq \|\mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{H}_m^\dagger\| \|\widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_{k-1}\| \leq \frac{1}{\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)} \|\widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_{k-1}\|. \quad (3.2.10)$$

For the second inequality, we use Theorem 3.1.2 to get

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathbf{y}_m]_k &= \mathbf{e}_k^* \mathbf{y}_m = \frac{\beta}{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_m\|^2} \left[\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m^{-1} \right]_{k,k:m} [\mathbf{u}_m]_{k:m} \\ &= \frac{\beta}{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_{k-1}\|^2 + \|\mathbf{u}_m\|_{k:m}^2} \left[\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m^{-1} \right]_{k,k:m} [\mathbf{u}_m]_{k:m}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.11)$$

where for the second equality we used the fact that $\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m$ is upper triangular and for the third equality we used that Eq. (3.1.16) implies $[\mathbf{u}_m]_{1:i} = \mathbf{u}_i$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Therefore, by the elementary

inequality $\frac{b}{a+b^2} \leq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{a}}$ for $a, b > 0$ we have

$$|[\mathbf{y}_m]_k| \leq \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{1 + \|\mathbf{u}_{k-1}\|^2}} \left\| \left[\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m^{-1} \right]_{k,k:m} \right\| \leq \frac{1}{2\sigma_m(\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m)} \|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{k-1}\|. \quad (3.2.12)$$

□

Remark 7. The above theorem improves the bound given by [53, Lemma 5.1] and our proof is also simpler. We note that $\sigma_m(\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m)$ is smaller than $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)$ but for $2\sigma_m(\widetilde{\mathbf{H}}_m)$, it is not clear whether it is smaller than $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)$ or not. However, in the following we will only keep the first term in the minimum in Eq. (3.2.8) for simplicity.

Combining the above two lemmas, we get the following theorem immediately.

Theorem 3.2.3. *Consider the inexact GMRES method with maximum iteration number m . For any $\tau > 0$, if the error matrices $\mathbf{E}_0, \mathbf{E}_1, \dots, \mathbf{E}_m$ satisfy*

$$\|\mathbf{E}_0 \mathbf{x}_0\| \leq \frac{\tau}{3}, \quad \|\mathbf{E}_k \mathbf{v}_k\| \leq \frac{\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)}{3m} \frac{1}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{k-1}\|} \tau, \quad \text{for } k = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (3.2.13)$$

and the estimated residual norm $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_m\|$ is smaller than $\tau/3$, then the method terminates at the m -th iteration with the accuracy τ , i.e., $\|\mathbf{r}_m\| \leq \tau$.

Note that the estimated residual norm $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$ is monotone decreasing when the iteration proceeds. Therefore, Theorem 3.2.3 suggests that we can be *more and more crude* when computing the inexact matrix-vector products $\widetilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(k)} \mathbf{v}_k$ as the iteration proceeds and thus save some computational cost. However, to use the bound on $\|\mathbf{E}_k \mathbf{v}_k\|$ in practice, we need to first know the smallest singular value $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)$ of the Hessenberg matrix \mathbf{H}_m , which is not available until the end of the m -th iteration. Therefore, we propose to use an estimate of $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)$ at first and then update it during the iteration if it turns out to be too large.

In summary, we propose the following inexact GMRES method in Algorithm 4, which guarantees the accuracy τ in the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_m\|$. Note that in Line 15, we update s by one tenth of the current smallest singular value of the Hessenberg matrix \mathbf{H}_k to ensure we do not restart too frequently. The 1/10 factor is somewhat arbitrary and can be tuned in practice. As mentioned in Remark 6, we also restart the inexact GMRES method after m iterations if the convergence is not reached.

Algorithm 4 Inexact GMRES

Require: Matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, right hand side $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, initial guess $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{C}^n$, maximum number of iterations $m \in \mathbb{N}$, tolerance $\tau > 0$; initial guess s of $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)$, a procedure that given any error $\tau' > 0$ and a vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{C}^n$ returns an inexactly computed vector $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{v}$ such that $\|(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}})\mathbf{v}\| \leq \tau'$.

Ensure: An approximate solution \mathbf{x} with $\|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}\| \leq \tau$

- 1: Compute $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{b} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(0)}\mathbf{x}_0$ with $\|(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(0)})\mathbf{x}_0\| \leq \tau/3$
 - 2: $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_0 = \mathbf{r}_0$, $\beta = \|\mathbf{r}_0\|$, $\mathbf{v}_1 = \mathbf{r}_0/\beta$
 - 3: $\mathbf{V}_1 = \mathbf{v}_1$
 - 4: **for** $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$ **do**
 - 5: Compute $\mathbf{w} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(k)}\mathbf{v}_k$ with $\|(\mathbf{A} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(k)})\mathbf{v}_k\| \leq \frac{s}{3m} \frac{1}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{k-1}\|} \tau$
 - 6: $\mathbf{h}_k = \mathbf{V}_k^* \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^k$
 - 7: $\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{h}_k$
 - 8: $h_{k+1,k} = \|\mathbf{v}_{k+1}\|$
 - 9: $\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{v}_{k+1}/h_{k+1,k}$
 - 10: $\mathbf{V}_{k+1} = [\mathbf{V}_k, \mathbf{v}_{k+1}]$
 - 11: Compute \mathbf{u}_k iteratively by Eq. (3.1.16) (or if $k = 1$, $\mathbf{u}_1 = h_{11}^*/h_{21}^{-*}$)
 - 12: Compute the estimated residual norm $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\|$ by Eq. (3.1.13)
 - 13: Compute $\sigma_k(\mathbf{H}_k)$
 - 14: **if** $s > \sigma_k(\mathbf{H}_k)$ **then**
 - 15: $s = \sigma_k(\mathbf{H}_k)/10$
 - 16: Compute \mathbf{y}_k by Eq. (3.1.12)
 - 17: Set $\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{y}_k$ and go back to Line 1
 - 18: **if** $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_k\| \leq \tau/3$ **then**
 - 19: Compute \mathbf{y}_k by Eq. (3.1.12)
 - 20: **return** $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{y}_k$
-

Chapter 4

Application to DFPT

In this chapter, we apply the inexact GMRES method to the DFPT. Specifically, we consider the discretized Dyson equation and apply the inexact GMRES method to this linear system. The inexactness comes from the fact that to apply the dielectric operator \mathcal{E} , we need to solve a sequence of Sternheimer equations Eq. (2.4.22), which are solved by the CG method with some tolerance τ^{CG} .

4.1 Theoretical analysis

As discussed in Section 2.4.4, the discretized Dyson equation

$$\mathcal{E}\delta\rho = \delta\rho_0 \quad (4.1.1)$$

is defined by the discretized dielectric operator $\mathcal{E} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_g \times N_g}$ and the discretized initial perturbation $\delta\rho_0 \in \mathbb{C}^{N_g}$. Recall that $\mathcal{E} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_g \times N_g}$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{E} = I_{N_g} - \chi_0 \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_g \times N_g}, \quad (4.1.2)$$

and the application of χ_0 is computed by

$$\delta\rho = \|\delta\mathbf{V}\| \chi_0 \frac{\delta\mathbf{V}}{\|\delta\mathbf{V}\|} = \|\delta\mathbf{V}\| \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \text{Re} \left((\mathbf{S}\phi_n)^* \cdot (\mathbf{S}\delta\phi_n^P + \mathbf{S}\delta\phi_n^Q) \right) + \delta f_n |\mathbf{S}\phi_n|^2, \quad (4.1.3)$$

where δf_n and $\delta\phi_n^P$ are defined in Eq. (2.4.22) and for $n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}$, $\delta\phi_n^Q$ is the unique solution to the discretized Sternheimer equation Eq. (2.4.22)

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{Q} (H[\rho] - \epsilon_n \mathbf{I}_{N_b}) \mathbf{Q}}_{=: \mathbf{A}_n} \delta\phi_n^Q = - \underbrace{\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{S}^* (\delta\mathbf{V} \cdot (\mathbf{S}\phi_n)) / \|\delta\mathbf{V}\|}_{=: \mathbf{b}_n}. \quad (4.1.4)$$

It should be noted that here is $\delta\mathbf{V}$ normalized prior to the application of χ_0 , which is a step taken to circumvent potential numerical issues.

In the spirit of the inexact GMRES method, we define a sequence of inexact dielectric operators $\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}^{(i)}$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, m$ by

$$\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}^{(i)} = \mathbf{I}_{N_g} - \widetilde{\chi}_0^{(i)} \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_g \times N_g}. \quad (4.1.5)$$

$\widetilde{\chi}_0^{(i)}$ is the inexact application of χ_0 computed by

$$\delta\rho = \|\delta\mathbf{V}\| \frac{\widetilde{\chi}_0^{(i)} \delta\mathbf{V}}{\|\delta\mathbf{V}\|} = \|\delta\mathbf{V}\| \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \text{Re} \left((\mathbf{S}\phi_n)^* \cdot \left(\mathbf{S}\delta\phi_n^P + \mathbf{S}\widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)} \right) \right) + \delta f_n |\mathbf{S}\phi_n|^2, \quad (4.1.6)$$

in which δf_n and $\delta\phi_n^P$ remain the same as those in the exact χ_0 . The inexactness comes from the approximate solutions $\widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)}$ to the discretized Sternheimer equation Eq. (4.1.4) with tolerance $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$, i.e.,

$$\|\mathbf{b}_n - \mathbf{A}_n \widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)}\| \leq \tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}. \quad (4.1.7)$$

First, we want to relate the tolerance of CG $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$ to the error of the application of the inexact dielectric operator on a vector $(\mathcal{E} - \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}^{(i)}) \delta\rho$.

Lemma 4.1.1. *The error of the application of the inexact dielectric operator $\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}^{(i)}$ on a vector $\delta\rho \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ is bounded by a linear combination of the CG tolerances. Formally, we have*

$$\|(\mathcal{E} - \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}^{(i)}) \delta\rho\| \leq \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \frac{\|\mathbf{K}\delta\rho\|}{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n} \tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}. \quad (4.1.8)$$

Proof. It is easy to verify that $\mathbf{A}_n^\dagger \mathbf{A}_n = \mathbf{A}_n \mathbf{A}_n^\dagger = \mathbf{Q}$ where \mathbf{A}_n^\dagger is the pseudo-inverse of \mathbf{A}_n . Note that both $\delta\phi_n^Q$ and $\widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)}$ are in $\text{range}(\mathbf{Q})$ and $\delta\phi_n^Q$ solves Eq. (4.1.4) exactly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\phi_n^Q - \widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)} &= \mathbf{Q} \left(\delta\phi_n^Q - \widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)} \right) = \mathbf{A}_n^\dagger \mathbf{A}_n \left(\delta\phi_n^Q - \widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)} \right) \\ &= \mathbf{A}_n^\dagger \left(\mathbf{b}_n - \mathbf{A}_n \widetilde{\delta\phi}_n^Q^{(i)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.9)$$

Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\left\| \left(\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} - \widetilde{\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}}^{(i)} \right) \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\| &= \left\| \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\| \left\| \left(\chi_0 - \widetilde{\chi}_0^{(i)} \right) \left(\mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} / \left\| \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\| \right) \right\| \\
&= \left\| \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\| \left\| \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \operatorname{Re} \left((\mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\phi}_n)^* \cdot \left(\mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\delta\phi}_n^{\mathcal{Q}} - \widetilde{\mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\delta\phi}_n^{\mathcal{Q}}}^{(i)} \right) \right) \right\| \\
&\leq \left\| \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\| \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \left\| \boldsymbol{\delta\phi}_n^{\mathcal{Q}} - \widetilde{\boldsymbol{\delta\phi}_n^{\mathcal{Q}}}^{(i)} \right\| \\
&= \left\| \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\| \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \left\| \mathbf{A}_n^\dagger \left(\mathbf{b}_n - \mathbf{A}_n \widetilde{\boldsymbol{\delta\phi}_n^{\mathcal{Q}}}^{(i)} \right) \right\| \\
&\leq \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \frac{\left\| \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\|}{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n} \tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}},
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1.10}$$

where we used the fact that \mathbf{F} is unitary thus preserves the norm. \square

Therefore, if we apply the inexact GMRES method Algorithm 4 to the discretized Dyson equation with some tolerance $\tau > 0$, then by Theorem 3.2.3, for $\boldsymbol{\delta\rho}$ being a vector from the Arnoldi basis \mathbf{V}_m , it suffices to choose the tolerances of the CG method $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$ such that

$$\left\| \left(\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} - \widetilde{\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}}^{(i)} \right) \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\| \leq \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} 2f_n \frac{\left\| \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta\rho} \right\|}{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n} \tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}} \leq \frac{\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)}{3m} \frac{1}{\left\| \widetilde{\mathbf{r}}_{i-1} \right\|} \tau \tag{4.1.11}$$

in order to obtain the requested accuracy τ in the true residual norm $\left\| \mathbf{r}_m \right\|$. Given the tolerance $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$, by Corollary 3.1.4, asymptotically, the number of iterations of the CG method is given by

$$N_{i,n}^{\text{CG}} \approx a \log(\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}) + b, \tag{4.1.12}$$

for some constants $a < 0$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}$ depending on the condition number of the matrix \mathbf{A}_n . Therefore, the total number of iterations of the CG methods occurred in one application of $\widetilde{\chi}_0^{(i)}$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} a \log(\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}) + b = a \log \left(\prod_{n=1}^{N_{\text{occ}}} \tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}} \right) + b N_{\text{occ}}, \tag{4.1.13}$$

which should be minimized under the constraint Eq. (4.1.11). The Lagrange multiplier method gives us the optimal choice of $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$ as in the following theorem.

Theorem 4.1.2. *Consider the inexact GMRES method applied to the discretized Dyson equation, which gives the inexact Arnoldi decomposition:*

$$\left[\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}^{(1)} \mathbf{v}_1, \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}^{(2)} \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}^{(m)} \mathbf{v}_m \right] = \mathbf{V}_{m+1} \mathbf{H}_m, \tag{4.1.14}$$

where

$$\mathbf{V}_m = [\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_m], \quad \mathbf{v}_1 = \left(\delta \boldsymbol{\rho}_0 - \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}^{(0)} \delta \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(0)} \right) / \|\delta \boldsymbol{\rho}_0 - \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}^{(0)} \delta \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(0)}\|. \quad (4.1.15)$$

Note that $\delta \boldsymbol{\rho}_0$ is the right hand side of the discretized Dyson equation while $\delta \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(0)}$ is the initial guess of the solution. For any $\tau > 0$, if the tolerance $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$ of the Sternheimer equation CG solver satisfies

$$\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}} \leq \frac{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n}{2N_{\text{occ}}f_n \|\mathbf{K}\mathbf{v}_i\|} \frac{\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)}{3m} \frac{1}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{i-1}\|} \tau, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, m, \text{ and } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}, \quad (4.1.16)$$

and

$$\tau_{0,n}^{\text{CG}} \leq \frac{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n}{2N_{\text{occ}}f_n \|\mathbf{K}\delta \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(0)}\|} \frac{1}{3} \tau, \text{ for } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}, \quad (4.1.17)$$

and the last estimated residual of the GMRES method satisfies

$$\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_m\| \leq \frac{\tau}{3}, \quad (4.1.18)$$

then the method terminates at the m -th iteration with the accuracy τ , i.e., true residual $\|\mathbf{r}_m\| \leq \tau$.

4.2 Practical considerations

Based on the discussions in previous Section 4.1, if we set the CG tolerances $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$ according to Theorem 4.1.2 when applying the inexact GMRES method to the discretized Dyson equation, then we can guarantee the accuracy of the returned solution. However, in practice, it turns out that the theoretical choice of the tolerance $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$ given in Theorem 4.1.2 is too conservative and pessimistic. Namely, the scaling constant

$$\frac{2N_{\text{occ}}f_n \|\mathbf{K}\mathbf{v}_i\|}{(\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n)} \quad (4.2.1)$$

is too large, leading to tight CG tolerances and over-solving the Sternheimer equations to a high accuracy that is not necessary. For example, in Fig. 4.1, we plot the scaling constant

$$\frac{N_{\text{occ}}f_n}{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n} \quad (4.2.2)$$

for each Sternheimer equation solver of the aluminum supercell system defined in Section 5.2.1. We observe that even without the constant $2\|\mathbf{K}\mathbf{v}_i\|$, the constants are already in the order of 10^2 to 10^3 .

Figure 4.1: Scaling constant $\frac{N_{\text{occ}}f_n}{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n}$ for k -points (1, 1, 1), (1, 1, 2) and (1, 2, 2) of the aluminum supercell system.

Therefore, we introduce two strategies to implement the inexact GMRES method for the Dyson equation.

- Conservative strategy: drop the constant $2\|\mathbf{K}\mathbf{v}_i\|$ in Theorem 4.1.2 and set

$$\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}} = \frac{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n}{N_{\text{occ}}f_n} \frac{\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)}{3m} \frac{1}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{i-1}\|} \tau, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, m, \text{ and } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}, \quad (4.2.3)$$

and

$$\tau_{0,n}^{\text{CG}} = \frac{\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n}{N_{\text{occ}}f_n} \frac{1}{3} \tau, \text{ for } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}. \quad (4.2.4)$$

- Aggressive strategy: discard the scaling constants directly and set

$$\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}} = \frac{\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)}{3m} \frac{1}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{i-1}\|} \tau, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, m, \text{ and } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}, \quad (4.2.5)$$

and

$$\tau_{0,n}^{\text{CG}} = \frac{1}{3} \tau, \text{ for } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}. \quad (4.2.6)$$

We also remark here that in current implementations for DFPT, the tolerance of the CG method is usually fixed to be $\tau/10$ or $\tau/100$ for all the Sternheimer equations. We denote the above mentioned four strategies by

$$\text{Con}, \quad \text{Agr}, \quad \text{D10}, \quad \text{D100} \quad (4.2.7)$$

respectively and investigate their performance in the following numerical experiments.

Chapter 5

Numerical Experiments

5.1 Implementation details

In this chapter, we will compare the four strategies of solving the Dyson equation proposed in Section 4.2 for aluminum systems. For condensed matter systems, we impose the periodic boundary condition and use the so-called *supercell* approach to model the system. The formulation is similar to the non-periodic case described in Section 2.2 while the Kohn-Sham equations and the discretization spaces \mathbb{G}° and \mathbb{G}^\square should be adjusted accordingly due to the Bloch's theorem. We refer the readers to [35, Section 2.8] for more details. We discretize the Brillouin zone using a uniform Monkhorst-Pack grid with the trapezoidal quadrature rule [39]. We use the PBE exchange–correlation functional [45] and GTH pseudopotentials [20, 25]. We use the SCF iterations to solve the Kohn-Sham equations, enhanced with the Kerker preconditioner [29]. For the Sternheimer equation solver, we use the conjugate gradient (CG) algorithm with a preconditioning technique based on Schur complement proposed in [11] and we force the CG to run at least one iterations. For all the numerical experiments, we use the `Julia` package `DFTK` [26].

5.2 Numerical results

5.2.1 Aluminum Supercell

We first consider an aluminum supercell system with 4 unitcells, each containing 4 Al atoms. We use a cut-off energy $E_{\text{cut}} = 15$ Hartree, a temperature $T = 10^{-3}$ Hartree and a $1 \times 3 \times 3$ k -grid. In this case, $N_g = 108000$, N_b 's are around 5000 for different k -points and the number of Sternheimer equations to be solved for each χ_0 application is $N_{\text{occ}} = 231$.

For the conservative and aggressive strategies (`Con` and `Aggr`), we run the inexact (restarted)

GMRES Algorithm 4 with the CG tolerances $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}}$ set as described in Section 4.2. For the other two strategies (D10 and D100), we run the standard GMRES Algorithm 2. The initial guess of the solution is set to be zero and the initial guess of $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)$ is set to be 1, i.e., $\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{0}$ and $s = 1$. We set the maximum dimension of the Krylov subspace, i.e., restart period of GMRES m to be 20 and the tolerance τ to be 10^{-12} . When computing the exact χ_0 application to obtain the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$, we set the CG tolerances to 10^{-16} .

We first plot both the estimated residual norms $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ and the true residual norms $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ of the four strategies in Fig. 5.1. We also display the total number of CG iterations N in the legend. We first observe that there is indeed a gap between the true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ and the estimated residual norm $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ as we have discussed in Section 3.2 and therefore the need of the inexact GMRES method is justified. We further observe that the Con and D100 strategies terminate with the desired accuracy τ and our Con strategy is one order of magnitude more accurate than the D100 strategy with 7% speedup. For the other two strategies Agr and D10, they terminate with a similar accuracy slightly above the desired one τ but our method is around 22% cheaper. Lastly, we observe that our inexact strategies Con and Agr converge using more GMRES iterations than the standard GMRES strategies D10 and D100 but our method is still more favorable since the number of CG iterations dominates the total cost.

Figure 5.1: Residual norms $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum supercell system. Square markers ■ denote where the method stops based on the stopping criterion with the total number of CG iterations N displayed in the legend. Circle markers • denote where the method restarts, either due to encountering $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m) < s$ for inexact GMRES (Line 15 in Algorithm 4) or exceeding the restart period $m = 20$.

Next, we plot the average number of CG iterations and geometric average of CG tolerances per GMRES iteration in Fig. 5.2. We can see that for D10 and D100, the average number of CG iterations is always around 20 across all the GMRES iterations. For Con and Agr, as the GMRES iteration proceeds, the CG tolerances become larger and we solve the Sternheimer equations less accurately. In particular, near convergence, we even only perform one or two CG iterations for each

Sternheimer equation. We observe that the CG tolerances for `Con` is around two orders of magnitude smaller than `Agr`, which leads to several more CG iterations for each Sternheimer equation.

Figure 5.2: Average number of CG iterations (left) and geometric average of CG tolerances (right) per GMRES iteration for the four strategies for the aluminum supercell system when $\tau = 10^{-12}$ and $m = 20$.

Finally, we recall that `Agr` gives the same CG tolerances for all the Sternheimer equations in one application of χ_0 , i.e., $\tau_{i,n}^{\text{CG}} = \tau_{i,n'}^{\text{CG}}$ for all $1 \leq n, n' \leq N_{\text{occ}}$ while for `Con`, we have adaptivity among different Sternheimer equations. We only plotted the geometric average of CG tolerances per GMRES iteration for `Con` in the previous Fig. 5.2. To have a closer look at the behavior of the CG tolerances for `Con`, we plot the scaling constant Eq. (4.2.2) and its components f_n and $1/(\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n)$ in Fig. 5.3 corresponding to each Sternheimer equation for different k -point. We can see that the Sternheimer equations are particularly ill-conditioned when we are close to the last occupied orbital (n close to $(N_{\text{occ}})_k$). While for f_n , it becomes extremely small for the last occupied orbitals. Therefore, the CG tolerances, as a product of the above two components, are large in the middle and small near the both ends. Further more, we should not forget the term $N_{\text{occ}} = 231$, which in fact contributes the most to the scaling constants.

Figure 5.3: Inverse eigenvalue gap $1/(\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n)$ (top), occupation number f_n (middle) and scaling constant $N_{\text{occ}}f_n/(\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n)$ (bottom) of each Sternheimer equation for k -points (1, 1, 1), (1, 1, 2) and (1, 2, 2) of the aluminum supercell system.

Shorter restart period m and lower requested accuracy τ

In practice, the system can contain more electrons and can lead to larger plane-wave basis set than ours $N_g = 108000$. In such a case, we cannot afford a restart period $m = 20$. We will have to use shorter restart period m to reduce the memory usage. In Fig. 5.4 and Fig. 5.5, we do the convergence plot again as in Fig. 5.1 but with $m = 10$ and $m = 5$ respectively. We observe that as the case with $m = 20$ in Fig. 5.1, Con and D100 terminate with the desired accuracy τ but Agr and D10 terminate with a slightly larger residual norm. We also observe that in those cases, our method is more advantageous. In particular, for $m = 10$, Con is 25% cheaper than D100, Agr is 35% cheaper than D10. For $m = 5$, Con is 20% cheaper than D100, Agr is 37% cheaper than D10. Recall that those numbers are 7% and 22% for $m = 20$.

Figure 5.4: Residual norms $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum supercell system. Requested tolerance τ is set to 10^{-12} and the restart period m is set to 10.

Figure 5.5: Residual norms $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum supercell system. Requested tolerance τ is set to 10^{-12} and the restart period m is set to 5.

To investigate the influence of different requested accuracy τ , we run the algorithms with $\tau = 10^{-12}, 10^{-10}, 10^{-8}, 10^{-6}$ and 10^{-4} and collect the returned true residual norm and the number of total CG iterations, which are plotted in Fig. 5.6. We also mark if one instance achieves the requested accuracy τ or not by circle markers \bullet and star markers \star respectively. We observe that only Con is able to give the desired accuracy τ in all the cases for different τ and m while for Agr and D10, they fail to converge to the desired accuracy in all the cases. For D100, it only fails in a few cases, most of which are with $m = 20$. For example, when $\tau = 10^{-8}$ and $m = 20$, see Fig. 5.7. We

also observe that generally speaking, our method is more advantageous in the case of small restart period m and high accuracy τ .

Figure 5.6: Returned true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ versus the number of total CG iterations with different choices of requested tolerance $\tau = 10^{-12}$, 10^{-10} , 10^{-8} , 10^{-6} and 10^{-4} when restart period $m = 20$ (left), $m = 10$ (right) and $m = 5$ (bottom) for the aluminum supercell system. Circle markers ● denote that the method achieves the requested tolerance τ and star markers ★ denote that the method does not achieve the requested tolerance τ .

Figure 5.7: Residual norms $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum supercell system. Requested tolerance τ is set to 10^{-8} and the restart period m is set to 20.

Discussions on potential improvements

Lastly, we showcase that our method has great potential to further enhance the performance by two minor adjustments in the implementation of the inexact GMRES algorithm. First, we observe that in Fig. 5.1, Agr and Con restart before exceeding the restart period $m = 20$, which implies our initial guess of $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m)$ is too large so that Algorithm 4 restarts early at Line 15. This may slow down the convergence of GMRES. If we simply change the initial guess of the Agr strategies from $s = 1$ to $s = 0.5$, we can see in Fig. 5.8 that the number of total CG iterations further reduces by 20% without hurting the accuracy, which leads to a 37% speedup compared with D10. Second, even though Agr does not manage to achieve the desired accuracy τ in all the cases as we have seen in Fig. 5.6, with a small adjustment of the CG tolerance when computing the first basis vector \mathbf{r}_0 in the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_m(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_0)$, we can overcome this issue. Specifically, we set (c.f. Eq. (4.2.6))

$$\tau_{0,n}^{\text{CG}} = \frac{1}{300}\tau, \text{ for } n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{occ}}. \quad (5.2.1)$$

This force the GMRES method to compute the first Krylov basis vector $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{b} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(0)}\mathbf{x}_0$ more accurately. We can see in Fig. 5.9 that with this choice of the CG tolerance $\tau_{0,n}^{\text{CG}}$, Agr is able to achieve the desired accuracy τ with only 3.5% more total CG iterations than Agr with $\tau_{0,n}^{\text{CG}} = \tau/3$, which is even more accurate than D100 but is 41% cheaper than it.

Figure 5.8: Residual norms $\|r_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{r}_i\|$ of D10, D100 and Agr with $s = 1$ and $s = 0.5$ for the aluminum supercell system. Requested tolerance $\tau = 10^{-12}$ and the restart period $m = 20$.

Figure 5.9: Residual norms $\|r_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{r}_i\|$ of D10, D100 and Agr with $\tau_{0,n}^{CG} = \tau/3$ and $\tau_{0,n}^{CG} = \tau/300$ for the aluminum supercell system. Requested tolerance $\tau = 10^{-12}$ and the restart period $m = 5$.

5.2.2 Aluminum Unitcell

We then consider an aluminum unitcell with 4 Al atoms. We use a cut-off energy $E_{\text{cut}} = 15$ Hartree, a temperature $T = 10^{-3}$ Hartree and a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ k -grid. In this case, $N_g = 27000$ and N_b 's are around 1200 for different k -point and the number of Sternheimer equations to be solved for each χ_0 application is $N_{\text{occ}} = 179$, rendering the problem less challenging. We only consider D10, Agr and Con strategies for simplicity. We defer the figures to Appendix A for brevity. The observations are similar to the aluminum supercell system with the only exception that D10 and Agr are already able to achieve the desired accuracy τ in some cases, while for the more challenging supercell system, they never achieve the desired accuracy τ .

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In density functional theory, many physical quantities of interest require the computation of the response of the density to an external perturbation δV . In this thesis, we reviewed the density functional perturbation theory (DFPT) in the Kohn-Sham DFT framework and proposed an inexact Krylov subspace method to solve the Dyson equation, which is the key to solve the linear response problem in DFPT. The key observation is that the application of the dielectric operator requires the solution of a large number of Sternheimer equations, yielding an inner-outer iteration scheme. We proposed an adaptive strategy to choose the inner stopping criterion, rather than keeping it fixed as in standard implementations of DFPT, and thus reduced the computational cost. With the adaptive strategy, we can save up to 40% in terms of the number of inner iterations without sacrificing the accuracy.

Finally, we conclude this thesis with discussions on possible future work.

1. Other existing strategies to choose the CG tolerances, such as the one implemented in QUANTUM ESPRESSO [19], should be reviewed and compared with our proposed strategies.
2. We can further improve the performance and accelerate the convergence of the inexact GMRES method by employing more advanced techniques, such as implicit restarting [41], preconditioning [59], deflation [42], augmentation [40] and mixed precision arithmetic [1, 23]. Parallel implementation leveraging modern high performance computing architectures can also be considered [3].
3. The theoretical choice of CG tolerances given in Theorem 4.1.2 is far from optimal and has a few discrepancies with the actual implementation. For example, the smallest eigenvalue of \mathbf{A}_n in implementation is in fact larger than the crude estimate $\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n$ used in Lemma 4.1.1 since we employed the Schur complement technique [11] and the Kerker preconditioner [29]. Moreover, the normalization convention of the FFT operator \mathbf{F} should also be taken into account as mentioned in Remark 4.
4. Fine tuning the parameter s and the division factor in Line 15 of Algorithm 4 based on the spectrum estimates of the dielectric operator should be further investigated. As we have already seen in Fig. 5.8, these choices can have a significant impact on the performance of the inexact GMRES method.
5. A deeper theoretical understanding is essential to explain the phenomenon observed in Fig. 5.9, particularly regarding the significant influence of the initial Krylov basis vector \mathbf{r}_0 's accuracy on solution quality.

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Appendix A

Numerical results for the aluminum unitcell system

Long restart period $m = 20$ and high requested accuracy $\tau = 10^{-12}$

Figure A.1: Residual norms $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum unitcell system. Square markers ■ denote where the method stops based on the stopping criterion with the total number of CG iterations N displayed in the legend. Circle markers ● denote where the method restarts, either due to encountering $\sigma_m(\mathbf{H}_m) < s$ for inexact GMRES (Line 15 in Algorithm 4) or exceeding the restart period $m = 20$.

Figure A.2: Average number of CG iterations (left) and geometric average of CG tolerances (right) per GMRES iteration for the four strategies for the aluminum unitcell system.

Figure A.3: Inverse eigenvalue gap $1/(\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n)$ (top), occupation number f_n (middle) and scaling constant $N_{occ}f_n/(\epsilon_{N+1} - \epsilon_n)$ (bottom) of each Sternheimer equation for k -points (1, 1, 1), (1, 1, 2), (1, 2, 2) and (2, 2, 2) of the aluminum unitcell system.

Shorter restart period m and lower requested accuracy τ

Figure A.4: Residual norms $\|r_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{r}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum unitcell system. Requested tolerance τ is set to 10^{-12} and the restart period m is set to 10.

Figure A.5: Residual norms $\|r_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{r}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum unitcell system. Requested tolerance τ is set to 10^{-12} and the restart period m is set to 5.

Figure A.6: Returned true residual norm $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ versus the number of total CG iterations with different choices of requested tolerance $\tau = 10^{-12}, 10^{-10}, 10^{-8}, 10^{-6}$ and 10^{-4} when restart period $m = 20$ (left), $m = 10$ (right) and $m = 5$ (bottom) for the aluminum unitcell system. Circle markers \bullet denote that the method achieves the requested tolerance τ and star markers \star denote that the method does not achieve the requested tolerance τ .

Figure A.7: Residual norms $\|\mathbf{r}_i\|$ or $\|\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i\|$ of the four strategies for the aluminum unitcell system. Requested tolerance τ is set to 10^{-8} and the restart period m is set to 20.